

Risk Analysis Report

Taxon: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> Rands	Area: South Africa
Listing under NEM:BA A&IS lists of 2020: 1b	
Compiled by: Felipe Balocchi	Approved by:
Picture of Taxon <p>Reference: Constructed based on EPPO Global Database. Available online: https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/PHYTCN/distribution. Accessed 29 July 2024.</p>	
Risk Assessment summary: <p><i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is a plant pathogenic microorganism that causes root rot and mortality of a wide range of plants. First recorded in South Africa in 1931, it has since spread to six provinces (LP, GP, MP, KZN, EC and WC). It is present in commercial settings, urban forests and natural vegetation, particularly in the Cape Floristic Region (CFR). Many regions in South Africa have suitable climate and habitat conditions for <i>P. cinnamomi</i> establishment. <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> was likely introduced to South Africa via contaminated plant material and soil, its primary pathway for spread. Additionally, it can be transported via machinery and equipment (e.g., boots). Currently, <i>P. cinnamomi</i> is not widely recognized as a threat, so it is likely to continue spreading, infecting native species, and increasing the risk of biodiversity loss. Without the introduction of strict biosecurity measures, this scenario is unlikely to change. South Africa has more than 140 known hosts, including highly susceptible native species in the Proteaceae and Ericaceae families. Globally, <i>P. cinnamomi</i> invasions have driven local extinctions and altered ecosystems. It also poses economic risks to crops like avocados and undermines ecosystem services in urban forests and conservation areas.</p>	Risk score: <p>High</p>
Risk Management summary: <p><i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> does not produce any environmental or socio-economic benefits, and thus there are no conflicts of interests. Eradication of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> is not feasible. The issuing of permits is not applicable for <i>P. cinnamomi</i> since it is high risk. However, restrictions to enforce higher biosecurity and hygiene standards to human activities that commonly serve as pathways could be considered. This includes restricting movement of soil and living plants to conservation areas, enforcing higher hygiene standards for visitors and preventing orchards or plantations from being established in direct proximity to these. Nevertheless, adequate risk management for <i>P. cinnamomi</i> requires the development of a comprehensive plan combining general biosecurity standards (including hygiene best practices) with targeted disease management and plant conservation strategies.</p>	
Recommendations: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> should remain listed as 1b. However, an Invasive Species Management Programme needs to be developed to ensure effective control (reduce risk of spread) and mitigation of impacts.	
Recommended listing category: 1b	
Recommended prohibitions or exemptions: No	
Is a change to nomenclature recommended: No	
Should the recommendation be revisited within 5 years: No	

Suggested citation: XXX

XXX
XXX

1. Background

BAC1 Name of assessor(s)	
Name of lead assessor	Dr Felipe Balocchi
Additional assessor (1)	
Additional assessor (2)	
Assessor for correspondence	Dr Felipe Balocchi
BAC2 Contact details of assessor(s)	
Lead assessor	Organisational affiliation: Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI), University of Pretoria
	email: felipe.balocchi@fabi.up.ac.za
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Additional assessor (1)	Organisational affiliation:
	email:
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Additional assessor (2)	Organisational affiliation:
	email:
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BAC3 Name(s) and contact details of expert(s) consulted	
Expert (1)	Name: Dr Trudy Paap
	email: trudy.paap@fabi.up.ac.za
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Expert (2)	Name:
	email:
	Phone:
Comments: Dr Trudy Paap is an experienced plant pathologist who did extensive work with <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> in south-western Australia. Dr Paap contributed with literature, host records, waypoints for map construction and proof-read the document before submission.	
BAC4 Scientific name of <i>Taxon</i> under assessment	
<i>Taxon</i> name: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>	Authority: Rands
Comments: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is the currently accepted name (Abad et al. 2023, Index Fungorum 2025, Mycobank 2025).	
References: Abad, Z.G., Burgess, T.I., Bourret, T., Bensch, K., Cacciola, S.O., Scanu, B., Mathew, R., Kasiborski, B., Srivastava, S. & Kageyama, K., 2023, ' <i>Phytophthora</i> : taxonomic and phylogenetic revision of the genus', <i>Studies in Mycology</i> 106, 259-348, https://doi.org/10.3114/sim.2023.106.05 . Index Fungorum, 2025, ' <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> '. Available online: https://www.indexfungorum.org/names/NamesRecord.asp?RecordID=260884 . Retrieved 14 March 2025. Mycobank, 2025, 'Fungal Databases, Nomenclature & Species Banks'. Available online: https://www.mycobank.org/details/708/21591 . Retrieved 14 March 2025. <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> : https://www.mycobank.org/details/708/21591 .	
BAC5 Synonym(s) considered	
Synonyms: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> var. <i>cinnamomi</i>	

<p>Comments: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is a basionym and has not had changes since its description (Rands 1922). However, two subspecies (varieties) were described, namely <i>P. cinnamomi</i> var. <i>parvispora</i> (Kröber & Marwitz 1993) and <i>P. cinnamomi</i> var. <i>robiniae</i> (Ho 2002). These had differences in host range, morphology and/or temperature preferences. A third variety, <i>P. cinnamomi</i> var. <i>cinnamomi</i>, was raised to represent the original description of <i>P. cinnamomi</i>. Further taxonomic studies resulted in <i>P. cinnamomi</i> var. <i>parvispora</i> and <i>P. cinnamomi</i> var. <i>robiniae</i> being recognized as distinct species: <i>P. parvispora</i> (Scanu et al. 2014) and <i>P. asiatica</i> (Rahman et al. 2014), respectively.</p>	
<p>References: Ho, H., 2002. '<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> var. <i>robiniae</i> var. nova on black locust in Jiangsu province of China'. <i>Mycotaxon</i>, 82, 391-396. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283291874_Phytophthora_cinnamomi_var_robiniae. Kröber, H. & Marwitz, R., 1993, '<i>Phytophthora tentaculata</i> sp. nov. und <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> var. <i>parvispora</i> var. nov., zwei neue Pilze von Zierpflanzen in Deutschland (<i>Phytophthora tentaculata</i> sp. nov. and <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> var. <i>parvispora</i> var. nov., two new fungi from ornamental plants in Germany)', <i>Zeitschrift für Pflanzenkrankheiten und Pflanzenschutz (Journal of Plant Diseases and Protection)</i> 100, 250-258, https://www.jstor.org/stable/43386173. Rahman, M.Z., Mukobata, H., Suga, H. & Kageyama, K., 2014, '<i>Phytophthora asiatica</i> sp. nov., a new species causing leaf and stem blight of kudzu in Japan', <i>Mycological Progress</i> 13, 759-769, https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-014-0959-1 Rands, R.D., 1922, 'Streepkanker van kaneel, veroorzaakt door <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> n. sp (Stripe canker of Cinnamon caused by <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> n. sp.)', <i>Mededelingen van het Instituut voor Plantenziekten</i> 54, 1-53, https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/titel/903632. Scanu, B., Hunter, G.C., Linaldeddu, B.T., Franceschini, A., Maddau, L., Jung, T. & Denman, S., 2014, 'A taxonomic re-evaluation reveals that <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> and <i>P. cinnamomi</i> var. <i>parvispora</i> are separate species', <i>Forest Pathology</i> 44, 1-20, https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12064.</p>	
<p>BAC6 Common name(s) considered</p>	
<p>Common names: None</p>	
<p>Comments: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is commonly abbreviated as "Pc" in scientific media. The species does not have a common name, however, common names exist for the diseases it causes, e.g., <i>Phytophthora</i> dieback (O'Gara et al. 2005), Jarrah dieback (Davison 2014), oak decline (Gallego 1999) or ink disease of sweet chestnut (Dal Maso & Montecchio 2015). In South Africa, especially in the avocado and Proteaceae cut-flower industries, the disease is commonly referred to as <i>Phytophthora</i> root rot. However, the use of disease names in some contexts may refer to diseases caused by additional factors, including other <i>Phytophthora</i> species.</p>	
<p>References: Dal Maso, E. & Montecchio, L., 2015, 'Large-scale fuzzy rule-based prediction for suitable chestnut ink disease sites: a case study in north-east Italy', <i>Forest Pathology</i> 45, 311-323, https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12172. Davison, E., 2014, 'Resolving confusions about jarrah dieback-don't forget the plants', <i>Australasian Plant Pathology</i> 43, 691-701, https://doi.org/10.1007/s13313-014-0302-y. Gallego, F., De Algaba, A.P. & Fernandez-Escobar, R., 1999, 'Etiology of oak decline in Spain', <i>European Journal of Forest Pathology</i> 29, 17-27, https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1439-0329.1999.00128.x. O'Gara, E., Howard, K., Wilson, B. & Hardy, G.E.S.J., 2005, 'Management of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> for Biodiversity Conservation in Australia: Part 1 – A Review of Current Management', <i>A report funded by the Commonwealth Government Department of the Environment and Heritage by the Centre for Phytophthora Science and Management, Murdoch University, Western Australia</i></p>	
<p>BAC7 What is the native range of the Taxon?</p>	
<p>Response: Southeast Asia (see map in Appendix BAC7)</p>	<p>Confidence: High</p>

Comments: The centre of origin of *P. cinnamomi* is still a matter of debate (Shakya et al. 2021) and several hypotheses have been proposed (Crandall & Gravatt 1967; Pratt & Heather 1973; Ko et al. 1978; Zentmyer 1988; Arentz & Simpson 1986). The main criteria used in these studies include (i) genetic diversity, (ii) mating type distribution and ratio, (iii) host diversity and aggressiveness levels in natural environments and/or, (iv) association of disease development with anthropogenic disturbances. Most studies have suggested countries in the Southeast Asia-Pacific region, with Taiwan and Papua New Guinea being the two most frequently proposed areas (Arentz 2017; Shakya et al. 2021). Recently, Shakya et al. (2021) performed a large phylogeographic analysis of populations from multiple countries. Their results indicate that Taiwan and Vietnam are centres of diversity for *P. cinnamomi*, reinforcing Southeast Asia as the centre of origin. However, the authors acknowledge the under representation of Papua New Guinea and lack of representation for other relevant countries in Southeast Asia in their study (see Appendix BAC7).

References:

- Arentz, F. & Simpson, J.A., 1986, 'Distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in Papua New Guinea and notes on its origin', *Transactions of the British Mycological Society* 87, 289-295, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-1536\(86\)80032-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-1536(86)80032-8).
- Arentz, F., 2017, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* A1: An ancient resident of New Guinea and Australia of Gondwanan origin?', *Forest Pathology* 47, e12342, <https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12342>.
- Crandall, B.S. & Gravatt, G.F., 1967, 'The distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Ceiba* 13, 57-78, <https://revistas.zamorano.edu/index.php/CEIBA/issue/view/20>.
- Ko, W.H., Chang, M.S. & Su, H.J., 1978, 'Isolates of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* from Taiwan as evidence for an Asian origin of the species', *Transactions of the British Mycological Society* 71, 496-499, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-1536\(78\)80080-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-1536(78)80080-1).
- Pratt, B.H. & Heather, W.A., 1973, 'The origin and distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* Rands in Australian native plant communities and the significance of its association with particular plant species', *Australian Journal of Biological Sciences* 26, 559-574, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BI9730559>.
- Rands, R.D., 1922, 'Streepkanker van kaneel, veroorzaakt door *Phytophthora cinnamomi* n. sp (Stripe canker of Cinnamon caused by *Phytophthora cinnamomi* n. sp.)', *Mededelingen van het Instituut voor Plantenziekten* 54, 1-53, <https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/titel/903632>.
- Shakya, S.K., Grünwald, N.J., Fieland, V.J., Knaus, B.J., Weiland, J.E., Maia, C., Drenth, A., Guest, D.I., Liew, E.C.Y., Crane, C., Chang, T.-T., Fu, C.-H., Nguyen, M.C., Pham, Q.T., Scanu, B., Sanfuentes Von Stowasser, E., Durán, Á., Jung, M.H. & Jung, T., 2021, 'Phylogeography of the wide-host range panglobal plant pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Molecular Ecology* 30, 5164-5178, <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16109>.
- Zentmyer, G., 1988, 'Origin and distribution of four species of *Phytophthora*', *Transactions of the British Mycological Society* 91, 367-378, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-1536\(88\)80111-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-1536(88)80111-6).

BAC8 What is the global alien range of the Taxon?

Response: Africa, America, Asia, Europe and Oceania.

Confidence:
High

Comments: EPPO (2024) recognizes the detection of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in 78 countries (15 in Africa, 29 in America, 10 in Asia, 18 in Europe and six in Oceania) (See Appendix BAC8). This includes its detection in at least 15 of the world's biodiversity hotspots (Myers et al. 2000; Hardham & Blackman 2018), and its association with approximately 5000 hosts (Jung et al. 2013).

References:

- EPPO (European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization), 2024, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* (PHYTCN). Accessed through the 'EPPO Global Database' available online: <https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/PHYTCN/distribution> on 29 July 2024.
- Hardham, A.R. & Blackman, L.M., 2018, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Molecular Plant Pathology* 19, 260-285, <https://doi.org/10.1111/mpp.12568>.
- Jung, T., Colquhoun, I.J. & Hardy, G.E.S.J., 2013, 'New insights into the survival strategy of the invasive soilborne pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in different natural ecosystems in Western Australia', *Forest Pathology* 43, 266-288, <https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12025>.
- Myers, N., Mittermeier, R.A., Mittermeier, C.G., Da Fonseca, G.A. & Kent, J., 2000, 'Biodiversity hotspots for conservation priorities', *Nature* 403, 853-858, <https://doi.org/10.1038/35002501>.

BAC9 Geographic scope = the Area under consideration

Area of assessment: South Africa	
Comments: The geographic scope of the assessment is limited to South Africa	
BAC10 Is the Taxon present in the Area?	
Response: Yes	Confidence: High
<p>Comments: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> was first reported in South Africa in 1931 from avocado orchards in the Mpumalanga province (= Eastern Transvaal) (Wager 1931; 1941). <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> was then reported in the Western Cape, at first in 1972 from grapevines (Van der Merwe et al. 1972) and one year later from native flora (Van Wyk 1973; Van der Merwe & Van Wyk 1973). The number of recorded hosts grew consistently, reaching 87 species (71 native to South Africa) by 1979 (Von Broembsen 1979). Currently, <i>P. cinnamomi</i> in South Africa has been documented in six provinces (Appendix BAC10) from 145 plant species (excluding undetermined species; see Appendix 1). Host species are distributed in 46 genera (23 families) that include commercial crops and ornamentals as well as native species and cultivars.</p> <p>The identity of a large number of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> isolates has been confirmed from South Africa through morphology (Von Broembsen 1984; Von Broembsen & Kruger 1985; Linde et al. 1994) and DNA sequence data (Maseko 2010; Oh et al. 2013; Nesamari et al. 2017; Bose et al. 2018; Hulbert et al. 2019; Engelbrecht et al. 2022; Migliorini et al. 2023).</p>	

References:

- Bose, T., Wingfield, M.J., Roux, J., Vivas, M. & Burgess, T.I., 2018, 'Community composition and distribution of *Phytophthora* species across adjacent native and non-native forests of South Africa', *Fungal Ecology* 36, 17-25, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2018.09.001>
- Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 112, 1568-1574, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-10-21-0414-R>.
- Hulbert, J., Paap, T., Burgess, T.I., Roets, F. & Wingfield, M.J., 2019, 'Botanical gardens provide valuable baseline *Phytophthora* diversity data', *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 46, 126461, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2019.126461>.
- Linde, C., Kemp, G.H.J. & Wingfield, M.J., 1994, '*Pythium* and *Phytophthora* species associated with eucalypts and pines in South Africa', *European Journal of Forest Pathology* 24, 345-356, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0329.1994.tb00828.x>.
- Maseko, B.O., 2010, 'Die-back of cold tolerant *Eucalyptus* associated with *Phytophthora* spp. in South Africa', PhD Thesis, University of Pretoria, Pretoria. <https://upetd.up.ac.za/handle/2263/29415?show=full>.
- Migliorini, D., Vivas, M., Wingfield, M.J., Shaw, C. & Burgess, T.I., 2023, 'Oomycete composition in Proteaceae orchards and natural stands on three continents', *Mycological Progress* 22, 75, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-023-01925-1>.
- Nesamari, R., Coutinho, T.A. & Roux, J., 2017, 'Investigations into *Encephalartos* insect pests and diseases in South Africa and identification of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* as a pathogen of the Modjadji cycad', *Plant Pathology* 66, 612-622, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.12619>.
- Oh, E., Gryzenhout, M., Wingfield, B.D., Wingfield, M.J. & Burgess, T.I., 2013, 'Surveys of soil and water reveal a goldmine of *Phytophthora* diversity in South African natural ecosystems', *IMA Fungus* 4, 123-131, <https://doi.org/10.5598/imafungus.2013.04.01.12>.
- USDA (U.S. Department of Agriculture), 2024, 'USDA Fungal Databases', available online: <https://fungi.ars.usda.gov/>, accessed on 31 July 2024.
- Van Der Merwe, J.J.H., Joubert, D.J. & Matthee, F.N., 1972, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* root rot of grape-vines in the western Cape', *Phytophylactica* 4, 133-136, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_323.
- Van Der Merwe, J.J.H. & Van Wyk, P.S., 1973, 'Hosts of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in the Western Cape Province of South Africa', *Plant Disease Reporter* 57, 1005-1006, https://books.google.co.za/books?id=8aakoOcOBHoC&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false.
- Van Wyk, P.S., 1973, 'Root and crown rot of silver trees', *Journal of South African Botany* 39, 255-260, <https://archive.org/details/biostor-288929>.
- Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Occurrence of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on indigenous and exotic hosts in South Africa, with special reference to the South-Western Cape Province', *Phytophylactica* 16, 221-226, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_873.
- Von Broembsen, S.L. & Kruger, F.J., 1985, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* associated with mortality of native vegetation in South Africa', *Plant Disease* 69, 715-717, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-69-715>.
- Wager, V.A., 1931, 'Diseases of plants in South Africa due to members of the *Pythiaceae*', *Union of South Africa, Dept. Agric. Sci. Bull.* 105, 43
- Wager, V.A., 1941, 'Descriptions of the South African *Pythiaceae* with records of their occurrence', *Bothalia* 4, 3-35, <https://journals.abcjournal.aosis.co.za/index.php/abc/article/view/1708/1673>.

BAC11 Evidence of presence

Physical specimen	Yes	Source: The culture collection (CMW) at the Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI) holds a large collection of isolates of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> that have emerged from numerous studies involving this pathogen. These include isolates CMW48769, CMW48776 and CMW48779 (Bose et al. 2018) and CMW50706, CMW50722 and CMW50730 (Hulbert et al. 2019).
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Molecular confirmation	Yes	Source: GenBank Accession numbers: CMW48769 = KU726740, CMW48776 = KU726778, CMW48779 = KU726782, CMW50706 = MN545899, CMW50722 = MN545368, CMW50730 = MN545370.
Literature reference	Yes	Source: Bose, T., Wingfield, M.J., Roux, J., Vivas, M. & Burgess, T.I., 2018, 'Community composition and distribution of <i>Phytophthora</i> species across adjacent native and non-native forests of South Africa', <i>Fungal Ecology</i> 36, 17-25, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2018.09.001 Hulbert, J., Paap, T., Burgess, T.I., Roets, F. & Wingfield, M.J., 2019, 'Botanical gardens provide valuable baseline <i>Phytophthora</i> diversity data', <i>Urban Forestry & Urban Greening</i> 46, 126461, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2019.126461 .
Field observation	Yes	Source: Evidence of presence of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> through plants displaying typical symptoms and later confirmation through laboratory analyses (T. Paap, pers. comm.).
BAC12 Is the <i>Taxon</i> native to the Area or part of the Area?		
Response: No		Confidence: High
Comments: The wide distribution of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> in the Western Cape and the low susceptibility of some fynbos species led early studies (Von Broembsen 1979; Von Broembsen & Kruger 1985) to propose <i>P. cinnamomi</i> as native in South Africa. However, subsequent studies by Linde et al. (1997) and Engelbrecht et al. (2022) demonstrated low genetic diversity in South Africa's <i>P. cinnamomi</i> population, consistent with an introduction event (genetic bottleneck). Furthermore, Shakya et al. 2021 through a global population genetics and reproductive biology study of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> , demonstrated that the centre of diversity, and likely origin, is in Southeast Asia.		
References: Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', <i>Phytopathology</i> 112, 1568-1574, https://doi.org/10.1094/PHTO-10-21-0414-R . Linde, C., Drenth, A., Kemp, G.H.J., Wingfield, M.J. & Von Broembsen, S.L., 1997, 'Population structure of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> in South Africa', <i>Phytopathology</i> 87, 822-827, https://doi.org/10.1094/PHTO.1997.87.8.822 . Shakya, S.K., Grünwald, N.J., Fieland, V.J., Knaus, B.J., Weiland, J.E., Maia, C., et al., 2021, 'Phylogeography of the wide-host range panglobal plant pathogen <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> ', <i>Molecular Ecology</i> 30, 5164-5178, https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16109 . Von Broembsen, S., 1979, ' <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> - a threat to the Western Cape flora?', <i>Veld & Flora</i> 65, 53-55 Von Broembsen, S.L. & Kruger, F.J., 1985, ' <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> associated with mortality of native vegetation in South Africa', <i>Plant Disease</i> 69, 715-717, https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-69-715 .		
BAC13 What is the <i>Taxon</i>'s introduction status in the Area?		
The <i>Taxon</i> is in captivity or cultivation	Yes	Confidence: High
The <i>Taxon</i> is present outside of captivity or cultivation	Yes	Confidence: High
The <i>Taxon</i> is established	Yes	Confidence: High
The <i>Taxon</i> is invasive	Yes	Confidence: High

Comments: *Phytophthora cinnamomi* was likely introduced into South Africa (Western Cape Province) by early European settlers (Engelbrecht et al. 2022) through the movement of contaminated plant material, most likely agricultural commodities (Zentmyer 1985). The earliest confirmed record was from avocado orchards in Mpumalanga (Wager 1931; 1941), nevertheless, it is currently widespread in the country (Appendix BAC10) spanning six provinces and a range of environments. These include numerous commercial settings such as avocado (Engelbrecht et al. 2022), macadamia (McLeod et al. 2024), forestry (Linde et al. 1997), Proteaceae farms (Migliorini et al. 2023) and nurseries (Bezuidenhout et al. 2010). *Phytophthora cinnamomi* has also been recorded from natural areas from a wide range of native hosts (Von Broembsen 1984). The number of recorded hosts for South Africa (See Appendix 1) is still increasing (Nesamari et al. 2017; Qongqo et al. 2022), including critically endangered species in their native range in remote areas (Paap et al. 2023).

Phytophthora cinnamomi is one of only four plant pathogens included in the list of 100 of the world's worst invasive alien species (https://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/100_worst.php), and in South Africa it should be regarded as 'fully invasive' (Step 'E') following the guidelines of Paap et al. (2022).

References:

- Bezuidenhout, C., Denman, S., Kirk, S., Botha, W., Mostert, L. & Mcleod, A., 2010, '*Phytophthora* taxa associated with cultivated *Agathosma*, with emphasis on the *P. citricola* complex and *P. capensis* sp. nov', *Personia-Molecular Phylogeny and Evolution of Fungi* 25, 32-49, <https://doi.org/10.3767/003158510X538371>.
- Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 112, 1568-1574, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-10-21-0414-R>.
- Linde, C., Drenth, A., Kemp, G.H.J., Wingfield, M.J. & Von Broembsen, S.L., 1997, 'Population structure of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 87, 822-827, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO.1997.87.8.822>.
- McLeod, A., Hamza, Z., Schoeman, M.H., Moyo, L. & Akinsanmi, O.A., 2024, 'Temporal colonization of macadamia tree roots by *Phytophthora cinnamomi* based on a newly developed quantitative real-time PCR assay', *Plant Pathology* 73, 366-377, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.13819>.
- Migliorini, D., Vivas, M., Wingfield, M.J., Shaw, C. & Burgess, T.I., 2023, 'Oomycete composition in Proteaceae orchards and natural stands on three continents', *Mycological Progress* 22, 75, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-023-01925-1>.
- Nesamari, R., Coutinho, T.A. & Roux, J., 2017, 'Investigations into *Encephalartos* insect pests and diseases in South Africa and identification of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* as a pathogen of the Modjadji cycad', *Plant Pathology* 66, 612-622, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.12619>.
- Paap, T., Wingfield, M.J., Burgess, T.I., Wilson, J.R., Richardson, D.M., Santini, A., 2022, 'Invasion frameworks: a forest pathogen perspective', *Current Forestry Reports* 8, 74-89, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40725-021-00157-4>.
- Paap, T., Nndanduleni, M. & Wingfield, M.J., 2023, 'A critically endangered Proteaceae in the Cape Floristic Region threatened by an invasive pathogen', *Bothalia-African Biodiversity & Conservation* 53, 1-7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.38201/btha.abc.v53.i1.6>
- Qongqo, A., Nchu, F. & Geerts, S., 2022, 'Relationship of alien species continues in a foreign land: The case of *Phytophthora* and Australian *Banksia* (Proteaceae) in South African Fynbos', *Ecology and Evolution* 12, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.9100>.
- Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Occurrence of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on indigenous and exotic hosts in South Africa, with special reference to the South-Western Cape Province', *Phytophylactica* 16, 221-226, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_873.
- Wager, V.A., 1931, 'Diseases of plants in South Africa due to members of the *Pythiaceae*', *Union of South Africa, Dept. Agric. Sci. Bull.* 105, 43
- Wager, V.A., 1941, 'Descriptions of the South African *Pythiaceae* with records of their occurrence', *Bothalia* 4, 3-35, <https://journals.abcjournal.aosis.co.za/index.php/abc/article/view/1708/1673>.
- Zentmyer, G.A., 1985, 'Origin and distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *California Avocado Society Yearbook* 69, 89-94, http://www.avocadosource.com/CAS_Yearbooks/CAS_69_1985/CAS_1985_PG_89-96.pdf.

BAC14 How did (or does) the Taxon arrive in the Area?

Pathway: Unaided:NaturalDispersal	Confidence: Low
Pathway: Contaminant:ParasiteOfPlants	Confidence: High
Pathway: Contaminant:NurseryMaterialContaminant	Confidence: High
Pathway: Contaminant:ContaminantOfPlants	Confidence: High
Pathway: Contaminant:HabitatMaterialContaminant	Confidence: High
Pathway: Contaminant:OtherContaminant	Confidence: High
Pathway: Stowaway:MachineryAndEquipment	Confidence: High
Pathway: Stowaway:PeopleAndLuggage	Confidence: High
Pathway: Stowaway:LandVehicles	Confidence: High
<p>Comments: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is a soil- and waterborne microorganism with fungal-like traits but distinct characteristics. It grows filamentous hyphae and forms resistant structures (chlamydospores, stromata-like aggregations) to withstand dry periods (Zentmyer 1980; Jung et al. 2013; Migliorini et al. 2015). It reproduces asexually via sporangia that release swimming zoospores, spreading through water. Sexual reproduction is rare, typically resulting in selfed-oospores rather than those formed by opposite mating types (Jung et al. 2013). Thick-walled oospores can remain dormant for long periods, surviving harsh conditions (Gyeltshen et al. 2021). All these structures can serve as dissemination propagules under suitable conditions.</p> <p>Research on spread of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> highlights plant and soil movement as primary pathways (Zentmyer 1985; Jung et al. 2013). It spreads via (i) infected plants (often asymptomatic; Contaminant: Plant parasites) or (ii) non-susceptible plants with colonized roots (Contaminant: Contaminant of plants) (Bienapfl & Balci 2014). Contaminated soil is another key vector, including (i) soil in potted plants (Contaminant: Nursery material), (ii) transported soil (Contaminant: Transportation of habitat material) (Bienapfl & Balci 2014; Laurence et al. 2024), and (iii) soil carried on footwear, equipment, commodities, or vehicles (Stowaway; Liew et al. 2023; McDougall & Liew 2024).</p> <p><i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> can also spread autonomously through root-to-root contact as well as surface and subsurface water flow (Cahill et al. 2008). However, these modes of spread typically result in short-distance movement (Hart et al. 2024) and only sporadic events of water movement in larger quantities can lead to the spread in longer distances (Cahill et al. 2008).</p> <p><i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> was first detected in South Africa in 1931 in Mpumalanga avocado orchards (Wager 1931; 1941). However, population genetics suggest its introduction likely occurred in the Western Cape via contaminated plants brought by European settlers in the 1600s (Engelbrecht et al. 2022).</p>	

References:

Bienapfl, J.C. & Balci, Y., 2014, 'Movement of *Phytophthora* spp. in Maryland's nursery trade', *Plant Disease* 98, 134-144, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-06-13-0662-RE>.

Cahill, D.M., Rookes, J.E., Wilson, B.A., Gibson, L. & McDougall, K.L., 2008, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* and Australia's biodiversity: impacts, predictions and progress towards control', *Australian Journal of Botany* 56, 279-310, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT07159>.

Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 112, 1568-1574, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-10-21-0414-R>.

Gyeltshen, J., Dunstan, W.A., Grigg, A.H., Burgess, T.I. & Hardy, G.E.S.J., 2021, 'The influence of time, soil moisture and exogenous factors on the survival potential of oospores and chlamydospores of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Forest Pathology* 51, e12637, <https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12637>.

Hart, R.P., Freebury, G. & Barrett, S., 2024, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi*: extent and impact in Two Peoples Bay Nature Reserve, Western Australia (1983–2024)', *Pacific Conservation Biology* 30, <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC24028>.

Jung, T., Colquhoun, I.J. & Hardy, G.E.S.J., 2013, 'New insights into the survival strategy of the invasive soilborne pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in different natural ecosystems in Western Australia', *Forest Pathology* 43, 266-288, <https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12025>.

Laurence, M.H., Mertin, A.A., Scarlett, K., Pang, C., Tabassum, S., Leishman, M.R., et al., 2024, '*Phytophthora* in urban tree planting stock: Are we managing the risk to the urban forest and natural ecosystems?', *Plant Pathology* 00, 1-13, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.13960>.

Liew, E.C., Phelan, M. & McDougall, K.L., 2023, 'The efficacy of a range of hygiene measures for boot cleaning to protect natural vegetation from *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Scientific Reports* 13, 5825, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-32681-7>.

McDougall, K. & Liew, E., 2024, 'Dispersal of *Phytophthora* species by off-road vehicles in New South Wales', *Australasian Plant Pathology* 53, 63-65, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13313-023-00961-5>.

Migliorini, D., Ghelardini, L., Tondini, E., Luchi, N. & Santini, A., 2015, 'The potential of symptomless potted plants for carrying invasive soilborne plant pathogens', *Diversity and Distributions* 21, 1218-1229, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12347>.

Wager, V.A., 1931, 'Diseases of plants in South Africa due to members of the *Pythiaceae*', *Union of South Africa, Dept. Agric. Sci. Bull.* 105, 43

Wager, V.A., 1941, 'Descriptions of the South African *Pythiaceae* with records of their occurrence', *Bothalia* 4, 3-35, <https://journals.abcjournal.aosis.co.za/index.php/abc/article/view/1708/1673>.

Zentmyer, G.A., 1980. '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* and the Diseases it Causes', The American Phytopathological Society, St Paul, Minnesota. 96 pp.

Zentmyer, G.A., 1985, 'Origin and distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *California Avocado Society Yearbook* 69, 89-94, http://www.avocadosource.com/CAS_Yearbooks/CAS_69_1985/CAS_1985_PG_89-96.pdf.

BAC15 Is the Taxon regulated in the Area?			
Response: Yes: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is currently regulated in South Africa.			Confidence: High
Comments: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is listed as Category 1b since 2014. However, listing was done without a risk analysis being carried out, and (to the best of my knowledge) there are no regulations in place to manage the spread of this microorganism.			
Version of the regulations	NEM:BA A&IS regulations (Notice No. 599, 1 Aug. 2014)	Regulatory name	<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>
Common name(s)	NA	Any previous names used	NA
Category	1b		
Exemptions or Prohibitions	NA		

2. Likelihood

LIK1 Likelihood of entry via unaided primary pathways	
Response: Present in the area (p = 1)	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is already present in the area, so the response is set to 1 as per the framework. The pathogen is present in two neighbouring countries: Zimbabwe (Rothwell 1982) and Eswatini (Von Broembsen 1984; NSW Department of Primary Industries 2024), however, information about spread and hosts in neighbouring countries is limited.</p> <p><i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> can spread autonomously through root-to-root contact as well as surface and subsurface water flow (Cahill et al. 2008). However, these modes of spread typically result in short-distance movement (Cahill et al. 2008; Hart et al. 2024). Sporadic events of water movement in larger quantities can lead to the spread of hundreds of meters in a single event (Weste & Law 1973; Hill et al. 1994).</p> <p>Studies in Australia have confirmed that <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> structures, such as chlamydospores and coraloid hyphae, can survive passage through the digestive tract of feral pigs and can thus be transported by them (Li et al. 2014). Similar results have been documented in birds and termites (Keast & Walsh 1979). Furthermore, <i>Phytophthora</i> species have been detected on the feathers of various bird species in Europe (Malewski et al. 2019), supporting the role of avian transport in pathogen spread. However, the overall contribution of these natural dispersal mechanisms remains uncertain and difficult to quantify. Substantial evidence indicates that cross-border entries have primarily occurred through human-assisted pathways (see LIK2).</p>	
<p>References:</p> <p>Cahill, D.M., Rookes, J.E., Wilson, B.A., Gibson, L. & McDougall, K.L., 2008, '<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> and Australia's biodiversity: impacts, predictions and progress towards control', <i>Australian Journal of Botany</i> 56, 279-310, https://doi.org/10.1071/BT07159.</p> <p>Hart, R.P., Freebury, G. & Barrett, S., 2024, '<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>: extent and impact in Two Peoples Bay Nature Reserve, Western Australia (1983–2024)', <i>Pacific Conservation Biology</i> 30, https://doi.org/10.1071/PC24028.</p> <p>Hill, T.C.J., Tippet, J.T. & Shearer, B.L., 1994, 'Invasion of Bassendean dune <i>Banksia</i> woodland by <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>', <i>Australian Journal of Botany</i> 42, 725-738, https://doi.org/10.1071/BT9940725.</p> <p>Keast, D. & Walsh, L.G., 1979, 'Passage and survival of chlamydospores of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> Rands, the causal agent of forest dieback disease, through the gastrointestinal tracts of termites and wild birds', <i>Applied and Environmental Microbiology</i> 37, 661-664, https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.37.3.661-664.1979.</p> <p>Li, A.Y., Williams, N., Fenwick, S.G., Hardy, G.E.S.J. & Adams, P.J., 2014, 'Potential for dissemination of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> by feral pigs via ingestion of infected plant material', <i>Biological Invasions</i> 16, 765-774, https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-013-0535-7.</p> <p>Malewski, T., Brzezińska, B., Belbahri, L. & Oszako, T., 2019, 'Role of avian vectors in the spread of <i>Phytophthora</i> species in Poland', <i>European Journal of Plant Pathology</i> 155, 1363-1366, https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-019-01840-w.</p> <p>NSW Department of Primary Industries, 2024, 'NSW DPI Biosecurity Collections, occurrence dataset: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> ', Accessed via GBIF.org on 2025-02-17. https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4892847110.</p> <p>Rothwell, A., 1982, 'A revised list of plant diseases occurring in Zimbabwe', <i>Kirkia</i> 12, 233-351, https://www.jstor.org/stable/23502151.</p> <p>Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Occurrence of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> on indigenous and exotic hosts in South Africa, with special reference to the South-Western Cape Province', <i>Phytophylactica</i> 16, 221-226, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_873.</p> <p>Weste, G. & Law, C., 1973, 'The invasion of native forest by <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>. III. Threat to the National Park, Wilson's Promontory, Victoria', <i>Australian Journal of Botany</i> 21, 31-51, https://doi.org/10.1071/BT9730031.</p>	
LIK2 Likelihood of entry via human aided primary pathways	
Response: Present in the area (p = 1)	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is already present in the area, so the response is set to 1 as per the framework. It is broadly accepted that the main means of introduction of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> into new areas is through anthropogenic movement of contaminated plant material or soil (Migliorini et al.</p>	

2015; Burgess et al. 2017; Serrano et al. 2019). Zentmyer (1985) identified the most likely pathway of entry to several areas (countries, continents), highlighting its association with the movement of plant-based commodities. Similarly, Serrano et al. (2019) showed that different genetic lineages of *P. cinnamomi* were linked to similar commodities in multiple countries, reinforcing the role of international trade in its global movement. In 2024, South Africa imported around 4.5 million kg of material and further 70 million items labelled as 'Live trees and other plants' from 68 countries (SARS 2025). Consequently, the likelihood of re-entry remains high.

Phytophthora cinnamomi can also be transported across borders as a stowaway, for example, through soil attached to machinery, equipment, vehicles, and people or their luggage (Liew 2023; McDougall & Liew 2024). In 2019, the Beitbridge border post, a major land crossing between Zimbabwe—a country where *P. cinnamomi* has been detected—and South Africa, recorded 2.8 million entries into South Africa (IOM 2020). Additionally, South Africa's extensive biodiversity-based tourism sector attracts millions of local and international visitors each year (Statistics South Africa 2024).

References:

- Burgess, T.I., Scott, J.K., McDougall, K.L., Stukely, M.J., Crane, C., Dunstan, W.A., et al., 2017, 'Current and projected global distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, one of the world's worst plant pathogens', *Global Change Biology* 23, 1661-1674, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13492>.
- Hart, R.P., Freebury, G. & Barrett, S., 2024, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi*: extent and impact in Two Peoples Bay Nature Reserve, Western Australia (1983–2024)', *Pacific Conservation Biology* 30, <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC24028>.
- IOM (International Organization for Migration), 2020, 'IOM Zimbabwe. 2019 Annual migration flow summary'. Available online: https://dtm.iom.int/dtm_download_track/10348?file=1&type=node&id=8105. Retrieved 18 February 2025.
- Liew, E.C., Phelan, M. & McDougall, K.L., 2023, 'The efficacy of a range of hygiene measures for boot cleaning to protect natural vegetation from *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Scientific Reports* 13, 5825, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-32681-7>.
- McDougall, K. & Liew, E., 2024, 'Dispersal of *Phytophthora* species by off-road vehicles in New South Wales', *Australasian Plant Pathology* 53, 63-65, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13313-023-00961-5>.
- Migliorini, D., Ghelardini, L., Tondini, E., Luchi, N. & Santini, A., 2015, 'The potential of symptomless potted plants for carrying invasive soilborne plant pathogens', *Diversity and Distributions* 21, 1218-1229, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12347>.
- SARS, 2025, 'Trade Statistics Data'. Available online: https://tools.sars.gov.za/tradestatsportal/data_download.aspx. Retrieved 18 February 2025.
- Serrano, M.S., Osmundson, T., Almaraz-Sánchez, A., Croucher, P.J.P., Swiecki, T., Alvarado-Rosales, D. & Garbelotto, M., 2019, 'A microsatellite analysis used to identify global pathways of movement of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* and the likely sources of wildland infestations in California and Mexico', *Phytopathology* 109, 1577-1593, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-03-19-0102-R>.
- Statistics South Africa, 2024, 'Natural Capital Series 5: Experimental Biodiversity-Based Tourism Estimates for South Africa, 2013 to 2019', Discussion document D04015 Produced in collaboration with the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) and the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE), Statistics South Africa, Pretoria. https://www.statssa.gov.za/?page_id=1854&PPN=D0401.5&SCH=73953
- Zentmyer, G.A., 1985, 'Origin and distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *California Avocado Society Yearbook* 69, 89-94, http://www.avocadosource.com/CAS_Yearbooks/CAS_69_1985/CAS_1985_PG_89-96.pdf.

LIK3 Habitat suitability

Response: Probable (p = 1)

Confidence: High

Rationale: The main habitat factors relevant for the establishment of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, are host availability, host density, plant diversity and characteristics of the soil (Nesbitt et al. 1979; Weste & Marks 1987). *Phytophthora cinnamomi* is favoured by low nutrient shallow soils, dense masses of susceptible roots and water saturation during warm periods (Nesbitt et al. 1979; Weste & Marks

1987). In contrast, soils with high clay content (high amounts of exchangeable cations), nutrient-rich soils and calcareous soils (elevated Ca²⁺), are commonly suppressive to *P. cinnamomi* survival and disease development (Nesbitt et al. 1979, Serrano et al. 2012).

South Africa has a large number of native plant species known to be susceptible to *P. cinnamomi* (See Appendix 1). In addition, the Fynbos Biome is characterized by nutrient-poor soils (Witkowski & Mitchell 1987; Richards et al. 1997; Coetsee et al. 2015) and harbours a large number of species belonging in highly susceptible plant families (e.g., Proteaceae, Ericaceae, Fabaceae; McDougall et al. 2024; Paap et al. 2025). The recent discovery of *P. cinnamomi* causing mortality of *Sorocephalus imbricatus* in its natural range (Paap et al. 2023) highlights the suitability of such environments for the pathogen's invasion.

Phytophthora cinnamomi has been recorded in various environments across South Africa, including natural areas, botanical gardens and commercial settings (Von Broembsen 1984; Linde et al. 1997; Bezuidenhout et al. 2010; Hulbert et al. 2019; Engelbrecht et al. 2022). However, the conditions required for *P. cinnamomi* to establish do not always align with those necessary for disease development (Burgess et al. 2017). As a result, the pathogen's presence in the soil may not always be evident through symptomatic plants, therefore, there are likely still-undetected invaded habitats.

References:

- Bezuidenhout, C., Denman, S., Kirk, S., Botha, W., Mostert, L. & Mcleod, A., 2010, '*Phytophthora* taxa associated with cultivated *Agathosma*, with emphasis on the *P. citricola* complex and *P. capensis* sp. nov', *Persoonia-Molecular Phylogeny and Evolution of Fungi* 25, 32-49, <https://doi.org/10.3767/003158510X538371>.
- Burgess, T.I., Scott, J.K., McDougall, K.L., Stukely, M.J., Crane, C., Dunstan, W.A., et al., 2017, 'Current and projected global distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, one of the world's worst plant pathogens', *Global Change Biology* 23, 1661-1674, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13492>.
- Coetsee, C., Bond, W.J. & Wigley, B.J., 2015, 'Forest and fynbos are alternative states on the same nutrient poor geological substrate', *South African Journal of Botany* 101, 57-65, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2014.11.007>.
- Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 112, 1568-1574, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-10-21-0414-R>.
- Hart, R.P., Freebury, G. & Barrett, S., 2024, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi*: extent and impact in Two Peoples Bay Nature Reserve, Western Australia (1983–2024)', *Pacific Conservation Biology* 30, <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC24028>.
- Hulbert, J., Paap, T., Burgess, T.I., Roets, F. & Wingfield, M.J., 2019, 'Botanical gardens provide valuable baseline *Phytophthora* diversity data', *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 46, 126461, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2019.126461>.
- Linde, C., Drenth, A., Kemp, G.H.J., Wingfield, M.J. & Von Broembsen, S.L., 1997, 'Population structure of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 87, 822-827, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO.1997.87.8.822>.
- McDougall, K.L., Barrett, S., Velzeboer, R., Cahill, D.M. & Rudman, T., 2024, 'Evaluating the risk to Australia's flora from *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23086>.
- Nesbitt, H.J., Malajczuk, N. & Glenn, A.R., 1979, 'Effect of organic matter on the survival of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* rands in soil', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 11, 133-136, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717\(79\)90089-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717(79)90089-0).
- Paap, T., Nndanduleni, M. & Wingfield, M.J., 2023, 'A critically endangered Proteaceae in the Cape Floristic Region threatened by an invasive pathogen', *Bothalia-African Biodiversity & Conservation* 53, 1-7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.38201/btha.abc.v53.i1.6>
- Paap, T., Balocchi, F., Wingfield, M.J., 2025, 'The root rot pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*: A long-overlooked threat to the Cape Floristic Region of South Africa', *Biological Invasions*.
- Richards, M.B., Cowling, R.M. & Stock, W.D., 1997, 'Soil nutrient dynamics and community boundaries in the fynbos vegetation of South Africa', *Plant Ecology* 130, 143-153, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009742225383>.
- Serrano, M.S., De Vita, P., Fernández-Rebollo, P. & Sánchez Hernández, M.E., 2012, 'Calcium fertilizers induce soil suppressiveness to *Phytophthora cinnamomi* root rot of *Quercus ilex*',

European Journal of Plant Pathology 132, 271-279, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-011-9871-6>.

Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Occurrence of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on indigenous and exotic hosts in South Africa, with special reference to the South-Western Cape Province', *Phytophylactica* 16, 221-226, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_873.

Weste, G. & Marks, G.C., 1987, 'The biology of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in Australasian forests', *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 25, 207-229, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.py.25.090187.001231>.

Witkowski, E.T.F. & Mitchell, D.T., 1987, 'Variations in soil phosphorus in the fynbos biome, South Africa', *The Journal of Ecology*, 1159-1171, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2260320>.

LIK4 Climate suitability

Response: Probable (p = 1)

Confidence: High

Rationale: *Phytophthora cinnamomi* originates from areas featuring tropical climates (Af, Köppen–Geiger climate classification; Beck et al. 2023). Accordingly, it is well known to be a destructive pathogen in tropical and subtropical agriculture, globally (Zentmyer 1985). Nevertheless, it is in areas featuring mediterranean type climates (C, temperate) where it has had the most impact to native ecosystems (Burgess et al. 2017). Although South Africa has a limited area (approx. 20 485 km²; 1.7%) in the Western Cape (WC) classified as mediterranean type climates (Csa and Csb; Appendix 2), it has large areas (approx. total 291 178 Km²; 23.9%) in several provinces (e.g., WC, EC, MP, KZN, GP, LP) classified as temperate types of climate ranging from subtropical (Cwa, Cwb, Cfa) to oceanic (Cfb) which are also favourable for *P. cinnamomi*.

Climate is recognised as a key factor controlling the distribution, life cycle and the impact of *P. cinnamomi* as a pathogen in natural ecosystems (Cahill et al. 2008). Among the main climatic factors influencing *P. cinnamomi* are temperature and rainfall (Thompson et al. 2014). *Phytophthora cinnamomi* is benefited by relatively warm temperatures, with an optimum range of 16-28 °C. Its geographical distribution is restricted in areas where temperatures frequently exceed 34 °C or drop below 5 °C, with frost a major limiting factor (Thompson et al. 2014). Rainfall is a critical factor for *P. cinnamomi* establishment and disease occurrence, evidenced by the strong link between its geographical distribution and rainfall thresholds (Burgess et al. 2017). Areas with average annual precipitation of 600 mm or higher are considered of high risk for *P. cinnamomi* disease (O'Gara et al. 2005). Nevertheless, several areas in Australia with annual rainfall averages ranging between 400–600 mm have also been heavily impacted by the pathogen (Cahill et al. 2008). It is estimated that areas with at least 300 mm of annual rainfall may be suitable for the pathogen to persist (T. Paap, pers. comm). South Africa has large areas with annual rainfall suitable for *P. cinnamomi* (Appendix 3).

The most recent CLIMEX model predicting the global distribution of *P. cinnamomi* is that of Burgess et al. (2017), with their predictions for distribution in South Africa largely congruent with those in previous models developed by Brasier & Scott (1994), Sutherst et al. 1999 and Desprez-Loustau et al. 2007 (Appendix 4). The predictions of Burgess et al. (2017) also show a high degree of overlap with areas deemed to have suitable climate (Appendix 2) and rainfall (Appendix 3), as well as the current known distribution (Appendix BAC10). Provinces such as the Western Cape (especially noteworthy given the number of susceptible hosts, see LIK3), Eastern Cape, Mpumalanga, KwaZulu-Natal and Limpopo contain areas that are climatically highly suitable for *P. cinnamomi*. The remaining provinces, with the exception of the Northern Cape, also have areas with suitable conditions but to a lesser extent.

References:

- Beck, H.E., Mcvicar, T.R., Vergopolan, N., Berg, A., Lutsko, N.J., Dufour, A., et al., 2023, 'High-resolution (1 km) Köppen–Geiger maps for 1901–2099 based on constrained CMIP6 projections', *Scientific Data* 10, 724, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02549-6>.
- Brasier, C.M. & Scott, J.K., 1994, 'European oak declines and global warming: a theoretical assessment with special reference to the activity of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Eppo Bulletin* 24, 221-232, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2338.1994.tb01063.x>.
- Burgess, T.I., Scott, J.K., McDougall, K.L., Stukely, M.J., Crane, C., Dunstan, W.A., et al., 2017, 'Current and projected global distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, one of the world's worst plant pathogens', *Global Change Biology* 23, 1661-1674, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13492>.

- Desprez-Loustau, M.-L., Robin, C., Reynaud, G., Déqué, M., Badeau, V., Piou, D., et al., 2007, 'Simulating the effects of a climate-change scenario on the geographical range and activity of forest-pathogenic fungi', *Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology* 29, 101-120, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07060660709507447>.
- Cahill, D.M., Rookes, J.E., Wilson, B.A., Gibson, L. & McDougall, K.L., 2008, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* and Australia's biodiversity: impacts, predictions and progress towards control', *Australian Journal of Botany* 56, 279-310, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT07159>.
- O'Gara, E., Howard, K., Wilson, B. & Hardy, G.E.S.J., 2005, 'Management of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* for Biodiversity Conservation in Australia: Part 1 – A Review of Current Management', *A report funded by the Commonwealth Government Department of the Environment and Heritage by the Centre for Phytophthora Science and Management, Murdoch University, Western Australia*.
- Sutherst, R.W., Maywald, G.F., Yonow, T. & Stevens, P.M., 1999. 'CLIMEX: predicting the effects of climate on plants and animals', CSIRO, Melbourne, Australia.
- Thompson, S.E., Levin, S. & Rodriguez-Iturbe, I., 2014, 'Rainfall and temperatures changes have confounding impacts on *Phytophthora cinnamomi* occurrence risk in the southwestern USA under climate change scenarios', *Global Change Biology* 20, 1299-1312, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12463>.
- Zentmyer, G.A., 1985, 'Origin and distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *California Avocado Society Yearbook* 69, 89-94, http://www.avocadosource.com/CAS_Yearbooks/CAS_69_1985/CAS_1985_PG_89-96.pdf.

LIK5 Unaided secondary (dispersal) pathways

Response: Unlikely ($p = 0.027$)

Confidence: Medium

Rationale: *Phytophthora cinnamomi* can spread autonomously by root-to-root contact (from an infected plant to a non-infected one; Hill et al. 1994) and through water movement (through waterborne zoospores; Hart et al. 2024). Hart et al. (2024) documented a rate of spread (mostly by root-to-root contact) of 1.53 m/year over a 33-year period in Western Australia. In contrast, spread through water movement can result in a spread of hundreds of meters in a single event (Weste & Law 1973; Hill et al. 1994). However, these events are sporadic, and the establishment depends on a number of additional factors (see LIK3 and LIK4; Burgess et al. 2017; Migliorini et al. 2023). Von Broembsen (1984) reported the recovery of *P. cinnamomi* from rivers of the Western Cape and suggested these as part of their pathways of spread. However, these results are contentious, as most studies carried out elsewhere (where *P. cinnamomi* is also invasive) report that this pathogen is rarely, if ever, recovered from rivers (Hüberli et al. 2013; Seddaiu et al. 2020; Schoebel et al. 2024).

In addition, *P. cinnamomi* may be spread by local fauna. Survival structures, such as chlamydospores and coraloid hyphae, can survive passage through the digestive tract of feral pigs (Li et al. 2014), and some bird and termite species (Keast & Walsh 1979). *Phytophthora* species have been detected on the feathers of various bird species in Europe (Malewski et al. 2019). These studies support the role of fauna on *P. cinnamomi* spread, however, these are hard to quantify.

The Centre for *Phytophthora* Science and Management suggest "Sites are likely to become infested in the next 10 years where the closest infestation is within 1-2 Km" (CPSM 2005). The score is set to $p = 0.027$, as it is unlikely that *P. cinnamomi* may spread autonomously 50 km or more in 10 years, as per the framework. The confidence is, however, set to medium, in light of the possibility for dispersal over further distances following high rainfall events or movement by wild or feral animals.

References:

- Burgess, T.I., Scott, J.K., McDougall, K.L., Stukely, M.J., Crane, C., Dunstan, W.A., et al., 2017, 'Current and projected global distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, one of the world's worst plant pathogens', *Global Change Biology* 23, 1661-1674, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13492>.
- CPSM, 2005, 'Management of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* for biodiversity conservation in Australia. Part 4: Risk assessment models for species, ecological communities and areas', A report funded by the Commonwealth Government Department of the Environment and Heritage by the Centre for *Phytophthora* Science and Management, Murdoch University, Western Australia. <https://www.dceew.gov.au/environment/invasive-species/publications/management-phytophthora-cinnamomi-biodiversity-conservation>.

- Hart, R.P., Freebury, G. & Barrett, S., 2024, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi*: extent and impact in Two Peoples Bay Nature Reserve, Western Australia (1983–2024)', *Pacific Conservation Biology* 30, <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC24028>.
- Hill, T.C.J., Tippet, J.T. & Shearer, B.L., 1994, 'Invasion of Bassendean dune *Banksia* woodland by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Australian Journal of Botany* 42, 725–738, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT9940725>.
- Hüberli, D., Hardy, G.E.S.J., White, D., Williams, N. & Burgess, T.I., 2013, 'Fishing for *Phytophthora* from Western Australia's waterways: a distribution and diversity survey', *Australasian Plant Pathology* 42, 251–260, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13313-012-0195-6>.
- Keast, D. & Walsh, L.G., 1979, 'Passage and survival of chlamydospores of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* Rands, the causal agent of forest dieback disease, through the gastrointestinal tracts of termites and wild birds', *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 37, 661–664, <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.37.3.661-664.1979>.
- Li, A.Y., Williams, N., Fenwick, S.G., Hardy, G.E.S.J. & Adams, P.J., 2014, 'Potential for dissemination of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* by feral pigs via ingestion of infected plant material', *Biological Invasions* 16, 765–774, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-013-0535-7>.
- Malewski, T., Brzezińska, B., Belbahri, L. & Oszako, T., 2019, 'Role of avian vectors in the spread of *Phytophthora* species in Poland', *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 155, 1363–1366, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-019-01840-w>.
- Migliorini, D., Vivas, M., Wingfield, M.J., Shaw, C. & Burgess, T.I., 2023, 'Oomycete composition in Proteaceae orchards and natural stands on three continents', *Mycological Progress* 22, 75, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-023-01925-1>.
- Schoebel, C.N., Prospero, S., Rigling, D. & Ruffner, B., 2024, 'Fishing for *Phytophthora* in watercourses of the highly urbanized Swiss Plateau', *Mycological Progress* 23, 17, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-024-01951-7>.
- Seddaiu, S., Brandano, A., Ruiu, P.A., Sechi, C. & Scanu, B., 2020, 'An overview of *Phytophthora* species inhabiting declining *Quercus suber* stands in Sardinia (Italy)', *Forests* 11, 971, <https://doi.org/10.3390/f11090971>.
- Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in rivers of the south-Western Cape Province', *Phytophylactica* 16, 227–230, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_874.
- Weste, G. & Law, C., 1973, 'The invasion of native forest by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. III. Threat to the National Park, Wilson's Promontory, Victoria', *Australian Journal of Botany* 21, 31–51, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT9730031>.

LIK6 Human aided secondary (dispersal) pathways

Response: Probable (p = 1)

Confidence: High

Rationale: Any human activity that transports *P. cinnamomi*-infested soil or plant material has the potential to introduce the pathogen to entirely new locations (Cahill et al. 2008). This includes several pathways that could facilitate the spread of this pathogen in the region, including:

- (a) Movement of contaminated material: The sale and distribution of infected nursery stock is one of the primary pathways for *P. cinnamomi* spread (Zentmyer 1985; Cahill et al. 2008; Migliorini et al. 2015). Numerous studies have demonstrated the introduction of *Phytophthora* species into new areas via commercial crops (Serrano et al. 2019) and the unintended spread into native ecosystems through restoration programs using contaminated plants sourced from indigenous nurseries (Frankel et al. 2020). In South Africa, *P. cinnamomi* has been confirmed in various settings where plants and potentially contaminated materials are propagated and distributed, including agricultural environments (Engelbrecht et al. 2022), forestry nurseries and plantations (Linde et al. 1997), ornamental and cut-flower nurseries and botanical gardens (Hulbert et al. 2019; Migliorini et al. 2023).
- (b) Recreational nature-based activities: *Phytophthora cinnamomi* can be spread through tourism activities, inadvertently carried on contaminated clothing and footwear or equipment and vehicles during bushwalking, camping, hiking or off-road vehicle use (Liew et al. 2023; McDougall & Liew 2024). South Africa has a large biodiversity-based tourism sector, attracting millions of local and international visitors each year (Statistics South Africa 2024). High-risk activities for *P. cinnamomi* spread include hiking in natural areas, mountaineering, four-wheel driving and wildlife-viewing excursions. The pathogen has been recorded in several tourist-accessible locations, including botanical gardens (Hulbert et al. 2019) and natural environments (Migliorini et al. 2023; Paap et al. 2023). Currently, there are no hygiene

protocols in place to mitigate *P. cinnamomi* spread during these activities, and awareness of the issue remains low to non-existent in most cases.

- (c) Other means of movement of contaminated materials: Several human activities can further contribute to the spread of *P. cinnamomi*. These include movement of soil/gravel for road construction and maintenance, timber harvesting, fire-fighting activities (Cahill et al. 2008) and keeping of domestic stock (Lewis & Colquhoun 2000).

References:

- Cahill, D.M., Rookes, J.E., Wilson, B.A., Gibson, L. & McDougall, K.L., 2008, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* and Australia's biodiversity: impacts, predictions and progress towards control', *Australian Journal of Botany* 56, 279-310, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT07159>.
- Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 112, 1568-1574, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHTO-10-21-0414-R>.
- Frankel, S.J., Conforti, C., Hillman, J., Ingolia, M., Shor, A., Benner, D., et al., 2020, '*Phytophthora* introductions in restoration areas: Responding to protect California native flora from human-assisted pathogen spread', *Forests* 11, 1291, <https://doi.org/10.3390/f11121291>.
- Hart, R.P., Freebury, G. & Barrett, S., 2024, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi*: extent and impact in Two Peoples Bay Nature Reserve, Western Australia (1983–2024)', *Pacific Conservation Biology* 30, <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC24028>.
- Hulbert, J., Paap, T., Burgess, T.I., Roets, F. & Wingfield, M.J., 2019, 'Botanical gardens provide valuable baseline *Phytophthora* diversity data', *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 46, 126461, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2019.126461>.
- McDougall, K. & Liew, E., 2024, 'Dispersal of *Phytophthora* species by off-road vehicles in New South Wales', *Australasian Plant Pathology* 53, 63-65, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13313-023-00961-5>.
- Migliorini, D., Ghelardini, L., Tondini, E., Luchi, N. & Santini, A., 2015, 'The potential of symptomless potted plants for carrying invasive soilborne plant pathogens', *Diversity and Distributions* 21, 1218-1229, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12347>.
- Migliorini, D., Vivas, M., Wingfield, M.J., Shaw, C. & Burgess, T.I., 2023, 'Oomycete composition in Proteaceae orchards and natural stands on three continents', *Mycological Progress* 22, 75, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-023-01925-1>.
- Lewis, S. & Colquhoun, I.J., 2000, 'Managing *Phytophthora* dieback: Guidelines for Local Government', *Diebeack Working Group*, <https://library.dbca.wa.gov.au/FullTextFiles/021436.pdf>.
- Liew, E.C., Phelan, M. & McDougall, K.L., 2023, 'The efficacy of a range of hygiene measures for boot cleaning to protect natural vegetation from *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Scientific Reports* 13, 5825, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-32681-7>.
- Linde, C., Drenth, A., Kemp, G.H.J., Wingfield, M.J. & Von Broembsen, S.L., 1997, 'Population structure of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 87, 822-827, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHTO.1997.87.8.822>.
- Serrano, M.S., Osmundson, T., Almaraz-Sánchez, A., Croucher, P.J.P., Swiecki, T., Alvarado-Rosales, D. & Garbelotto, M., 2019, 'A microsatellite analysis used to identify global pathways of movement of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* and the likely sources of wildland infestations in California and Mexico', *Phytopathology* 109, 1577-1593, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHTO-03-19-0102-R>.
- Statistics South Africa, 2024, 'Natural Capital Series 5: Experimental Biodiversity-Based Tourism Estimates for South Africa, 2013 to 2019.', Discussion document D0401.5. Produced in collaboration with the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) and the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE). Statistics South Africa, Pretoria. https://www.statssa.gov.za/?page_id=1854&PPN=D0401.5&SCH=73953.
- Zentmyer, G.A., 1985, 'Origin and distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *California Avocado Society Yearbook* 69, 89-94, http://www.avocadosource.com/CAS_Yearbooks/CAS_69_1985/CAS_1985_PG_89-96.pdf.

3. Consequences

CON1 Environmental impact	
CON1a: Competition	
Response: Data deficient (DD)	Confidence:
<p>Rationale: As a soilborne microorganism, <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> interacts with the broader soil microbiome wherever it invades. However, <i>P. cinnamomi</i> is considered a poor competitor, particularly in organic matter-rich soils with high microbial diversity (Nesbitt et al. 1979). While the nature of these interactions remains largely unstudied, competition is still a possibility given the immense microbial diversity in soil. Nevertheless, unlike many local microorganisms, <i>P. cinnamomi</i> can infect and reproduce on the roots of numerous host plants. Many microorganisms act as secondary pathogens or decomposers, benefiting from the additional nutrient input, however, this is a temporary effect, and the long-term ecosystem impact is likely to become negative (Anderson et al. 2010). Sites infested by <i>P. cinnamomi</i> show alterations in their microbiome compared to non-infested sites, including differences in microbial diversity and reduced abundance of tree-symbiotic microorganisms (e.g., mycorrhizae and protobacteria; Gómez-Aparicio et al. 2022). However, the role of competition in these changes remains unclear.</p>	
<p>References:</p> <p>Anderson, P., Brundrett, M., Grierson, P. & Robinson, R., 2010, 'Impact of severe forest dieback caused by <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> on macrofungal diversity in the northern jarrah forest of Western Australia', <i>Forest Ecology and Management</i> 259, 1033-1040, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2009.12.015.</p> <p>Gómez-Aparicio, L., Domínguez-Begines, J., Villa-Sanabria, E., García, L.V. & Muñoz-Pajares, A.J., 2022, 'Tree decline and mortality following pathogen invasion alters the diversity, composition and network structure of the soil microbiome', <i>Soil Biology and Biochemistry</i> 166, 108560, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2022.108560.</p> <p>Nesbitt, H.J., Malajczuk, N. & Glenn, A.R., 1979, 'Effect of organic matter on the survival of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> rands in soil', <i>Soil Biology and Biochemistry</i> 11, 133-136, https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717(79)90089-0.</p>	
CON1b: Predation	
Response: Data deficient (DD)	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1c: Hybridisation	
Response: Minimal concern (MC)	Confidence: Low
<p>Rationale: Hybridisation is known to occur among <i>Phytophthora</i> species (Brasier et al. 1999; Jung et al. 2017), especially among those with a more aquatic lifestyle. Boccas & Zentmyer (1976) attempted to produce hybrids between <i>P. cinnamomi</i> and <i>P. parasitica</i> under laboratory conditions, however, the percentage of well-formed sexual spores (oospores) was very low (5%), with germination rates also very low (5%). The authors suggest there was no conclusive evidence for these oospores being the result of hybridisation. The likelihood of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> hybridising with native <i>Phytophthora</i> spp. is very low and its impact should be regarded as negligible.</p>	
<p>References:</p> <p>Boccas, B. & Zentmyer, G.A., 1976, 'Genetical studies with interspecific crosses between <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> and <i>Phytophthora parasitica</i>', <i>Phytopathology</i> 66, 477-484, https://doi.org/10.1094/Phyto-66-477.</p> <p>Brasier, C.M., Cooke, D.E.L. & Duncan, J.M., 1999, 'Origin of a new <i>Phytophthora</i> pathogen through interspecific hybridization', <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i> 96, 5878-5883, https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.96.10.5878.</p> <p>Jung, T., Jung, M.H., Scanu, B., Seress, D., Kovács, G.M., Maia, C., et al., 2017, 'Six new <i>Phytophthora</i> species from ITS Clade 7a including two sexually functional heterothallic hybrid species detected in natural ecosystems in Taiwan', <i>Persoonia-Molecular Phylogeny and Evolution of Fungi</i> 38, 100-135, https://doi.org/10.3767/003158517X693615.</p>	
CON1d: Transmission of disease	
Response: Data deficient (DD)	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1e: Parasitism	
Response: Major (MR)	Confidence: High

Rationale: Parasitism is the main direct mean of impact of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on susceptible plant species. It colonizes roots, root collars and in some cases main stems, causing the death of living cells, which it then utilises for growth and reproduction (i.e., necrotrophy). This death and subsequent decay of roots and collars disrupts the transportation of water and nutrients from the soil, resulting in wilting and ultimately partial or complete dieback of aerial organs. The time until host mortality is dependant mainly on the plant's susceptibility level and prevailing environmental conditions (Podger 1972).

Phytophthora cinnamomi has more than 5000 hosts recorded worldwide (Jung et al. 2013), many of which are susceptible and die as a result of infection. In Australia, *P. cinnamomi* has been responsible for numerous local extinctions, including *Xanthorrhoea australis* and *Isopogon ceratophyllus* in localities at the Brisbane Ranges (Cahill et al. 2008), *Banksia verticillata* at Two Peoples Bay Nature Reserve (Western Australia; Hart et al. 2024), and *B. grandis* in the Northern Jarrah Forest (WA; McDougall 1996). In addition, *P. cinnamomi* is considered the main threat driving the total extinction of a range of species including *Hibbertia circinata* (McDougall et al. 2023), *B. anatona* (George et al. 2020) and *B. brownii* (Barrett et al. 2020a), and among the main threats of extinction of *B. montana* (Barrett et al. 2020b), *Personia micranthera* (Barrett & Weston 2020), *Lambertia fairallii* (Barrett et al. 2020c), and *Andersonia axilliflora* (Cahill et al. 2008). Several of these cases are the result of additive effects between wildfires and *P. cinnamomi*, where the infection rates are increased after fires, hindering the regeneration and recolonization of the ecosystem (Barrett et al. 2024). McDougall et al. (2024) highlighted 65 species in Australia as being at high risk of extinction due to *P. cinnamomi*.

Local extinctions of native flora due to *P. cinnamomi* have not been documented in South Africa. However, there is a wide range of susceptible native hosts in the country (BAC10, Appendix 1), many of which have restricted geographical ranges. The recent discovery of *P. cinnamomi* causing mortality of the critically endangered *Sorocephalus imbricatus* within its natural range (Paap et al. 2023) highlights the potential for such impacts to occur unnoticed. This case is particularly concerning, as the mortality observed by Paap et al. (2023) occurred in the larger of the only two known populations for the species, suggesting this species is at high risk of local and total extinction.

References:

- Barrett, S., Atkins, K., George, A., Keith, D., 2020a, '*Banksia brownii*', *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2020*: e.T112520669A113306481. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2020-2.RLTS.T112520669A113306481.en>. Accessed on 02 December 2024.
- Barrett, S., Atkins, K., Keith, D., 2020b, '*Banksia montana*', *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2020*: e.T112607724A113307356. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2020-2.RLTS.T112607724A113307356.en>. Accessed on 02 December 2024.
- Barrett, S., Atkins, K., Keith, D., 2020c, '*Lambertia fairallii*', *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2020*: e.T118147357A121862595. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2020-2.RLTS.T118147357A121862595.en>. Accessed on 02 December 2024.
- Barrett, S., Shearer, B.L., Crane, C.E. & Cochrane, A., 2008, 'An extinction-risk assessment tool for flora threatened by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Australian Journal of Botany* 56, 477-486, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT07213>.
- Barrett, S., Weston, P., 2020, '*Personia micranthera*', *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2020*: e.T118154041A121862730. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2020-3.RLTS.T118154041A121862730.en>. Accessed on 02 December 2024.
- Barrett, S., Yates, C.J., Dillon, R., Dilly, M., Varcoe, B., Martin, D., et al., 2024, 'Mitigation of disease and browsing impacts, and translocation, supports post-fire threatened flora recovery', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23081>.
- Cahill, D.M., Rookes, J.E., Wilson, B.A., Gibson, L. & McDougall, K.L., 2008, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* and Australia's biodiversity: impacts, predictions and progress towards control', *Australian Journal of Botany* 56, 279-310, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT07159>.
- George, A., Barrett, S., Keith, D.A., Atkins, K., 2020, '*Banksia anatona*' *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2020*: e.T112606325A113307116. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2020-3.RLTS.T112606325A113307116.en>. Accessed on 02 December 2024.
- Hart, R.P., Freebury, G. & Barrett, S., 2024, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi*: extent and impact in Two Peoples Bay Nature Reserve, Western Australia (1983–2024)', *Pacific Conservation Biology* 30, <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC24028>.

- Jung, T., Colquhoun, I.J. & Hardy, G.E.S.J., 2013, 'New insights into the survival strategy of the invasive soilborne pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in different natural ecosystems in Western Australia', *Forest Pathology* 43, 266-288, <https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12025>.
- McDougall, K.L., 1996, 'Vegetation patterns in the northern jarrah forest of Western Australia in relation to dieback history and the current distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *PhD Thesis, Murdoch University, Perth.*, Available online: <https://researchportal.murdoch.edu.au/esploro/outputs/991005544734807891>.
- McDougall, K.L., Wright, G.T., Bredell, P.M., James, E.A. & Simmons, L., 2023, 'Mount Imlay – an island of floristic significance on the brink', *Cunninghamia* 23, 001– 009, <https://www.botanicgardens.org.au/our-science/publications/cunninghamia#volume-23-2023>.
- McDougall, K.L., Barrett, S., Velzeboer, R., Cahill, D.M. & Rudman, T., 2024, 'Evaluating the risk to Australia's flora from *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23086>.
- Paap, T., Nndanduleni, M. & Wingfield, M.J., 2023, 'A critically endangered Proteaceae in the Cape Floristic Region threatened by an invasive pathogen', *Bothalia-African Biodiversity & Conservation* 53, 1-7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.38201/btha.abc.v53.i1.6>
- Podger, F., 1972, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* a cause of lethal disease of indigenous plant communities', *Phytopathology* 62, 972-981, <https://doi.org/10.1094/Phyto-62-972>.

CON1f: Poisoning/toxicity

Response: Data deficient (DD) | Confidence:

Rationale:

References:

CON1g: Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance

Response: Data deficient (DD) | Confidence:

Rationale:

References:

CON1h: Grazing/herbivory/browsing

Response: Data deficient (DD) | Confidence:

Rationale:

References:

CON1i: Chemical, physical or structural impact on ecosystem

Response: Major (MR) | Confidence: Medium

Rationale: *Phytophthora cinnamomi* has established in a range of different ecosystems around the world, having varied impacts in terms of type and extent (Sena et al. 2018).

In Australia, *P. cinnamomi* is responsible for altering the structure of forests and disrupting natural succession. One of the most severely impacted ecosystems is the coastal heathlands of Southwestern Australia (SWA). *Phytophthora cinnamomi* alters species assemblages, reducing species richness and richness within families and reducing cover of upper and lower shrub layers increasing bare ground cover (Barrett & Rathbone 2018). In the Northern Jarrah Forest of SWA, *P. cinnamomi* is involved in jarrah (*Eucalyptus marginata*) dieback, significantly reducing tree growth rates and, in some cases, causing mortality (Sena et al. 2018). *Phytophthora cinnamomi* also causes severe disease on *Banksia* spp., the main understory species in these forests (Podger 1972; Sena et al. 2018), resulting in forests with reduced canopy coverage (Crane & Shearer 2007), with altered conditions for understory species favouring natural succession of non-susceptible species. In Southeast Australia, *Phytophthora cinnamomi* is responsible for transforming plant communities from shrubby sclerophyll forests (with susceptible dominant species at different strata, including *Eucalyptus obliqua*, *Banksia serrata* and *Xanthorrhoea australis*) to open grassy woodlands (Weste 1981).

Phytophthora cinnamomi has also been associated with altered natural disturbances and reduced resilience of forests. In SWA disease occurrence is increased after fires, limiting the capacity of susceptible species to recolonize the impacted area (Moore et al. 2007; Moore et al 2015; Barrett et al. 2024). In Mediterranean areas of Europe, *P. cinnamomi* is associated with root rot of *Quercus robur* and *Q. suber* (Robin et al. 1998; Scanu et al. 2013), though rarely directly causing tree mortality (Corcobado et al. 2014). However, infection leads to reduced root systems, diminishing trees' ability to withstand summer drought, which ultimately results in mortality for many (Corcobado et al. 2013).

The effects of *P. cinnamomi* infestation on chemical and physical characteristics of the soil remain relatively poorly understood. The reduction in overstorey and understorey coverage is assumed to increase soil erosion (Anderson et al. 2010; Postle et al. 1986). In addition, *P. cinnamomi* infested areas have disturbed conditions for litter accumulation, decomposition and therefore, nutrient cycles (Postle et al. 1986). The decomposition of dead plant material as a result of root rot disease is considered to increase nutrient availability in the soil in the short term. Anderson et al. (2010) found significant differences in available nitrate levels between infested and non-infested sites, supporting this hypothesis. However, as *P. cinnamomi*-induced plant cover loss continues, nutrient availability is expected to decline over the long term (Anderson et al. 2010; Postle et al. 1986).

The answer has been set to Major (MR) with a medium level of confidence due to the impact of *P. cinnamomi* on natural succession. The confidence level remains Medium due to the complex interplay between parasitism and structural changes. For example, Barrett et al. (2024) documented the local extinction of *Banksia anatona* at one of their study sites in SWA, attributing it to the combined effects of *P. cinnamomi* invasion and fire. While no studies have addressed this issue in South Africa, environments such as the fynbos—characterized by a high number of potentially susceptible species, natural fires, and nutrient-poor soils prone to erosion—may also be vulnerable to succession impacts.

References:

- Anderson, P., Brundrett, M., Grierson, P. & Robinson, R., 2010, 'Impact of severe forest dieback caused by *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on macrofungal diversity in the northern jarrah forest of Western Australia', *Forest Ecology and Management* 259, 1033-1040, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2009.12.015>.
- Barrett, S. & Rathbone, D., 2018, 'Long-term phosphite application maintains species assemblages, richness and structure of plant communities invaded by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Austral Ecology* 43, 360-374, <https://doi.org/10.1111/aec.12574>.
- Barrett, S., Yates, C.J., Dillon, R., Dilly, M., Varcoe, B., Martin, D., et al., 2024, 'Mitigation of disease and browsing impacts, and translocation, supports post-fire threatened flora recovery', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23081>.
- Corcobado, T., Cubera, E., Moreno, G. & Solla, A., 2013, '*Quercus ilex* forests are influenced by annual variations in water table, soil water deficit and fine root loss caused by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 169, 92-99, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2012.09.017>.
- Corcobado, T., Cubera, E., Juárez, E., Moreno, G. & Solla, A., 2014, 'Drought events determine performance of *Quercus ilex* seedlings and increase their susceptibility to *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 192, 1-8, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2014.02.007>.
- Crane, C.E. & Shearer, B.L., 2007, 'Hemispherical digital photographs offer advantages over conventional methods for quantifying pathogen-mediated changes caused by infestation of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Australasian Plant Pathology* 36, 466-474, <https://doi.org/10.1071/AP07052>.
- McDougall, K.L. & Liew, E.C.Y., 2024, 'The susceptibility of rare and threatened NSW species to the root-rot pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*: 2. The identification of species requiring protection or further research', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23106>.
- Moore, N., Barrett, S., Bowen, B., Shearer, B. & Hardy, G., 2007, 'The role of fire on *Phytophthora* dieback caused by the root pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in the Stirling Range National Park, Western Australia', *Proceedings of the 11th International Mediterranean Ecosystems (MEDECOS) Conference (2007), Perth, Western Australia*, 165-166, <https://researchportal.murdoch.edu.au/esploro/outputs/991005542933707891>.
- Moore, N., Barrett, S., Howard, K., Craig, M.D., Bowen, B., Shearer, B. & Hardy, G., 2015, 'Time since fire and average fire interval are the best predictors of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* activity in heathlands of south-western Australia', *Australian Journal of Botany* 62, 587-593, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT14188>.
- Podger, F., 1972, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* a cause of lethal disease of indigenous plant communities', *Phytopathology* 62, 972-981, <https://doi.org/10.1094/Phyto-62-972>.
- Postle, A.C., Majer, J.D. & Bell, D.T., 1986, 'Soil and litter invertebrates and litter decomposition in jarrah (*Eucalyptus marginata*) forest affected by jarrah dieback fungus (*Phytophthora cinnamomi*)', *Pedobiologia* 29, 47-69, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-4056\(23\)06881-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-4056(23)06881-6).

Robin, C., Desprez-Loustau, M.-L., Capron, G. & Delatour, C., 1998, 'First record of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on cork and holm oaks in France and evidence of pathogenicity', *Annals of Forest Science*, 55, 869-883, <https://doi.org/10.1051/forest:19980801>.

Scanu, B., Linaldeddu, B.T., Franceschini, A., Anselmi, N., Vannini, A. & Vettraino, A.M., 2013, 'Occurrence of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in cork oak forests in Italy', *Forest Pathology* 43, 340-343, <https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12039>.

Sena, K., Crocker, E., Vincelli, P. & Barton, C., 2018, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* as a driver of forest change: implications for conservation and management', *Forest Ecology and Management* 409, 799–807, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2017.12.022>.

Weste, G., 1981, 'Changes in the vegetation of sclerophyll shrubby woodland associated with invasion by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Australian Journal of Botany* 29, 261-276, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT9810261>.

CON1k: Indirect impacts through interactions with other species

Response: Moderate (MO)

Confidence: Medium

Rationale: The severe and multifaceted impacts of *P. cinnamomi* infestation on an ecosystem (see CON1e and CON1i) can result in indirect effects on organisms across the taxonomic spectrum.

In Australia, *P. cinnamomi* has caused local extinctions of various plant species, primarily due to parasitism and in some cases its interaction with wildfires (Barrett et al. 2024). Many of these plants maintain intimate—and often exclusive—associations with pollinators or ectomycorrhizal fungi (Anderson et al. 2010; McDougall & Liew 2024) and serve as key food sources and habitat for fauna, including endangered marsupials (Christensen 1973; Garkaklis et al. 2004). Their loss can lead to population declines or local extinctions of dependent taxa (co-extinction; Christensen 1973; McDougall & Liew 2024). Additionally, *P. cinnamomi* alters litter accumulation and environmental conditions—such as radiation and wind exposure—affecting the diversity of decomposers, including fungi (Anderson et al. 2010) and invertebrates (Postle et al. 1986).

No local extinctions of taxa due to the indirect effects of *P. cinnamomi* infestation have been documented. However, multiple studies across the taxonomic spectrum (Christensen 1973; Postle et al. 1986; Garkaklis et al. 2004; Anderson et al. 2010) have demonstrated reduced diversity, both quantitatively and qualitatively, at infested sites. Consequently, the response has been set to Moderate with a Medium level of confidence. No similar studies have been conducted in South Africa, where the impact of *P. cinnamomi* is largely overlooked. However, given the ecological similarities between SWA and the Cape Floristic Region, as well as the diverse fauna inhabiting these areas, a comparable scenario is likely.

References:

Anderson, P., Brundrett, M., Grierson, P. & Robinson, R., 2010, 'Impact of severe forest dieback caused by *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on macrofungal diversity in the northern jarrah forest of Western Australia', *Forest Ecology and Management* 259, 1033-1040, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2009.12.015>.

Barrett, S., Yates, C.J., Dillon, R., Dilly, M., Varcoe, B., Martin, D., et al., 2024, 'Mitigation of disease and browsing impacts, and translocation, supports post-fire threatened flora recovery', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23081>.

Christensen, P., 1973, 'Some ecological aspects of jarrah dieback', *Forest Focus* 10, 11-15, <https://library.dbca.wa.gov.au/static/Journals/080043/080043-10.pdf>.

Garkaklis, M.J., Calver, M.C., Wilson, B.A. & Hardy, G.E.S.J., 2004. 'Habitat alteration caused by an introduced plant disease, *Phytophthora cinnamomi*: a potential threat to the conservation of Australian forest fauna'. In: Lunney, D. (ed.) '*Conservation of Australia's Forest Fauna*'. Mosman, NSW, Australia: Royal Zoological Society of New South Wales.

Postle, A.C., Majer, J.D. & Bell, D.T., 1986, 'Soil and litter invertebrates and litter decomposition in jarrah (*Eucalyptus marginata*) forest affected by jarrah dieback fungus (*Phytophthora cinnamomi*)', *Pedobiologia* 29, 47-69, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-4056\(23\)06881-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-4056(23)06881-6).

CON1 Maximum environmental impact

Response: Major (MR)

Confidence: Medium

Rationale: The greatest impacts of *P. cinnamomi* in South Africa are linked to parasitism (CON1e) and thus, likely the disruption of natural succession (CON1i). There are about 100 known native host species in South Africa (Appendix 1), including susceptible Proteaceae and Ericaceae, some of which have been found infected in their natural ranges (Von Broembsen 1984; Paap et al. 2023). The case of the critically endangered *Sorocephalus imbricatus* exemplifies this risk (Paap et al.

2023). *Phytophthora cinnamomi* was detected in dying individuals within the larger of the species' only two remaining populations, while the smaller population has yet to be assessed. Observations by Paap et al. (2023) suggest that *P. cinnamomi* is driving this species toward local extinction, and if the second population is similarly affected, total extinction becomes a likely outcome.

The case of *S. imbricatus* represents one of the few isolated instances in South Africa where surveys have been conducted in natural areas by researchers familiar with *P. cinnamomi* symptoms. Given the long-standing presence of *P. cinnamomi* in South Africa and the lack of recognition of its impact, the extent of its impact in the region has likely not been fully revealed. It is highly likely that similar or even more severe cases have already developed or are currently unfolding. Research on *P. cinnamomi* in Australia, particularly in SWA, highlights its multifaceted impacts (CON1e, CON1i, CON1k), which can severely disrupt ecosystems and have cascading effects across the taxonomic spectrum.

References:

Paap, T., Nndanduleni, M. & Wingfield, M.J., 2023, 'A critically endangered Proteaceae in the Cape Floristic Region threatened by an invasive pathogen', *Bothalia-African Biodiversity & Conservation* 53, 1-7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.38201/btha.abc.v53.i1.6>
 Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Occurrence of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on indigenous and exotic hosts in South Africa, with special reference to the South-Western Cape Province', *Phytophylactica* 16, 221-226, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_873.

CON2 Socio-economic impact

CON2a: Safety

Response: Data deficient (DD)

Confidence:

Rationale:

References:

CON2b: Material and immaterial assets

Response: Moderate (MO)

Confidence: High

Rationale: *Phytophthora cinnamomi* causes severe economic losses in various plant-based commodities, including avocado, macadamia, grapevines, pears, pineapples, ornamentals (native and alien) and forestry (Gorter 1977; Von Broembsen 1984; Linde et al. 1994; Bezuidenhout et al. 2010; McLeod et al. 2024). These losses primarily result from reduced yields and increased management costs, ultimately leading to price increases for consumers. Amongst the most affected sectors is avocado, where *P. cinnamomi* is one of the primary loss-producing diseases, having been detected in all orchards across South Africa (Engelbrecht et al. 2022; Jordaan et al. 2022). The impact of *Phytophthora* root rot on the avocado industry has been so significant that substantial investments have been made to mitigate losses, including breeding programs, the development of disease-tolerant rootstocks, *P. cinnamomi*-specific disease management plans, and research funding through institutions like the South African Avocado Growers Association (Darvas 1983a; 1983b; Darvas et al. 1983) and the Avocado Research Programme at the University of Pretoria (<https://www.fabinet.up.ac.za/index.php/research-groups/avocado-research-programme>).

Additionally, *Phytophthora* root rot has long been considered a major limiting factor in the Proteaceae cut flower industry due to the high susceptibility of many species (Von Broembsen & Brits 1985a; 1985b). Losses from *P. cinnamomi* root rot have discouraged the commercial production of *Leucospermum* and *Leucadendron* spp. and have hindered the establishment of *Serruria* and *Banksia* species as viable crops (Von Broembsen & Brits 1985a).

There is abundant literature in South Africa demonstrating the efforts put by producers of different crops to manage disease caused by *P. cinnamomi*, however, there is no direct evidence of activities (in a broader sense, e.g., agriculture) being abandoned in *P. cinnamomi* infested areas. The answer is then set to Moderate (MO) as *P. cinnamomi* has a negative impact in the size and stability of several plant commodities, primarily due to income loss and increased management efforts for agriculturists. This also results in increased difficulty for consumers in accessing goods (e.g., higher prices, reduced availability).

References:

Bezuidenhout, C., Denman, S., Kirk, S., Botha, W., Mostert, L. & McLeod, A., 2010, '*Phytophthora* taxa associated with cultivated *Agathosma*, with emphasis on the *P. citricola* complex and

<p><i>P. capensis</i> sp. nov', <i>Persoonia-Molecular Phylogeny and Evolution of Fungi</i> 25, 32-49, https://doi.org/10.3767/003158510X538371.</p> <p>Darvas, J.M., 1983a, 'Five years of continued chemical control of Phytophthora root rot of avocados', <i>South African Avocado Growers' Association Yearbook</i> 6, 72-73, https://www.avocadosource.com/Journals/SAAGA/SAAGA_1983/SAAGA_1983_TOC.htm.</p> <p>Darvas, J.M., 1983b, 'Systemic fungicides applied as trunk paint against root rot of avocados', <i>South African Avocado Growers' Association Yearbook</i> 6, 78-79, https://www.avocadosource.com/Journals/SAAGA/SAAGA_1983/SAAGA_1983_TOC.htm.</p> <p>Darvas, J.M., Toerien, J.C. & Milne, D.L., 1983, 'Injection of established avocado trees for the effective control of Phytophthora root rot', <i>South African Avocado Growers' Association Yearbook</i> 6, 76-78, https://www.avocadosource.com/Journals/SAAGA/SAAGA_1983/SAAGA_1983_TOC.htm.</p> <p>Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', <i>Phytopathology</i> 112, 1568-1574, https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-10-21-0414-R.</p> <p>Gorter, G.J.M.A., 1977, 'Index of plant pathogens and the diseases they cause in cultivated plants in South Africa.', <i>Republic South Africa Dept. Agric. Techn. Serv. Pl. Protect. Res. Inst. Sci. Bull.</i> 392, 1-177</p> <p>Jordaan, E., Anelich, R. & Denner, F., 2022, 'Supporting crop establishment and trees in established avocado orchards, by way of combined use of biological and chemical solutions', <i>South African avocado growers association yearbook</i> 45, 24-37, https://www.avocadosource.com/Journals/SAAGA/SAAGA_2022/SAAGA_2022_45_TOC.htm.</p> <p>Linde, C., Kemp, G.H.J. & Wingfield, M.J., 1994, '<i>Pythium</i> and <i>Phytophthora</i> species associated with eucalypts and pines in South Africa', <i>European Journal of Forest Pathology</i> 24, 345-356, https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0329.1994.tb00828.x.</p> <p>Mcleod, A., Hamza, Z., Schoeman, M.H., Moyo, L. & Akinsanmi, O.A., 2024, 'Temporal colonization of macadamia tree roots by <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> based on a newly developed quantitative real-time PCR assay', <i>Plant Pathology</i> 73, 366-377, https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.13819.</p> <p>Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Occurrence of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> on indigenous and exotic hosts in South Africa, with special reference to the South-Western Cape Province', <i>Phytophylactica</i> 16, 221-226, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_873.</p> <p>Von Broembsen, S.L. & Brits, G.J., 1985a, 'Control of Phytophthora root rot of proteas in South Africa', <i>Acta Horticulturae</i> 185, 201-208, https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1986.185.21.</p> <p>Von Broembsen, S.L. & Brits, G., 1985b, 'Phytophthora root rot of commercially cultivated proteas in South Africa', <i>Plant Disease</i> 69, 211-213, https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-69-211.</p>	
CON2c: Health	
Response: Minimal Concern (MC)	Confidence: Low
<p>Rationale: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> does not directly impact human health, as it does not cause disease in humans. Pesticides are used for <i>P. cinnamomi</i> management in a range of commercial settings (e.g., phosphite, fosetyl-Al, Ridomil). However, these chemicals are considered relatively safe and associated risks (e.g., skin and eye irritation) can be avoided by adhering to appropriate standard operating procedures (SOPs) (CropLife South Africa, 2022).</p>	
<p>References: CropLife South Africa, 2022, 'Responsible Pesticide Use: A guide for Operators', Operators guide, April 2022 Edition. Available online at: https://www.croplife.co.za/Resources/Crop%20Protection/Responsible%20Pesticide%20Use_ENG%20Booklet_Revised.pdf. Retrieved on 17 March 2025.</p>	
CON2d: Social, spiritual and cultural relations	
Response: Minor (MN)	Confidence: Medium
<p>Rationale: Due to the wide host range of <i>P. cinnamomi</i>, open recreational areas such as parks and botanical gardens, which contain diverse collections of native and alien plant species, are commonly affected by root rot disease (Hulbert et al. 2021; Nndanduleni et al. 2021; Paap et al. 2024). <i>P. cinnamomi</i> may lead to decline in health or mortality of ornamental plants, which impacts negatively the attractiveness of these public spaces.</p>	
<p>Sites such as Kirstenbosch NBG, where <i>P. cinnamomi</i> has long been present, is severely affected by Phytophthora root rot due to the extensive use of susceptible taxa (mostly within Proteaceae and</p>	

Ericaceae)—including the iconic and highly susceptible silver trees (*Leucadendron argenteum*; Nndanduleni et al. 2021). Similarly, at Harold Porter NBG *P. cinnamomi* was found associated with dieback of the iconic yellowwoods (*Podocarpus latifolius*; Personal observation, Balocchi & Paap, 2022).

Additionally, some traditional native medicinal plants, such as buchu (*Agathosma betulina* and *A. crenulate*) which hold cultural significance in Khoisan traditions (Moolla & Viljoen 2008), have been found to be susceptible to *P. cinnamomi* root rot disease (Bezuidenhout et al. 2010).

The answer has been set to Minor (MN) with medium level of confidence, as *P. cinnamomi* affects plant species relevant to the community. However, there is no available information on how this influences the ability to carry out associated activities.

References:

Bezuidenhout, C., Denman, S., Kirk, S., Botha, W., Mostert, L. & Mcleod, A., 2010, 'Phytophthora taxa associated with cultivated *Agathosma*, with emphasis on the *P. citricola* complex and *P. capensis* sp. nov', *Persoonia-Molecular Phylogeny and Evolution of Fungi* 25, 32-49, <https://doi.org/10.3767/003158510X538371>.

Hulbert, J., Paap, T., Burgess, T.I., Roets, F. & Wingfield, M.J., 2019, 'Botanical gardens provide valuable baseline *Phytophthora* diversity data', *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 46, 126461, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2019.126461>.

Moolla, A. & Viljoen, A.M., 2008, 'Buchu'—*Agathosma betulina* and *Agathosma crenulata* (Rutaceae): A review', *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 119, 413-419, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2008.07.036>.

Nndanduleni, M., Wondafrash, M., Gabayi, M. & Paap, T., 2021, 'Battle to save iconic silver trees', *Veld & Flora* 107, 38-43, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/ejc-veld_v107_n1_a14.

Paap, T., Balocchi, F., Burgess, T.I., Bose, T. & Wingfield, M.J., 2024, 'A diverse range of *Phytophthora* species from botanical gardens in South Africa, including the novel Clade 5 species, *Phytophthora mammiformis* sp. nov.', *Fungal Systematics and Evolution* 13, 111-122, <https://doi.org/10.3114/fuse.2024.13.05>.

CON2 Maximum socio-economic impact

Response: Moderate (MO)

Confidence: High

Rationale: The maximum socio-economic impact of *P. cinnamomi* is associated with material and immaterial assets (CON2b). Phytophthora root rot is a major disease affecting crops such as avocado (Jordaan et al. 2022) and macadamia (McLeod et al. 2024), leading to severe economic losses due to yield reduction and high management costs, necessitating significant investment to sustain productivity. It is also a major limiting factor in Proteaceae cut flower production, rendering the cultivation of several species unviable (Von Broembsen & Brits 1985). Furthermore, due to its wide host range, *P. cinnamomi* affects numerous other commercially produced species (Appendix 1), which, though impacted to a lesser extent, still experience yield losses and require ongoing management.

References:

Jordaan, E., Anelich, R. & Denner, F., 2022, 'Supporting crop establishment and trees in established avocado orchards, by way of combined use of biological and chemical solutions', *South African avocado growers' association yearbook* 45, 24-37, https://www.avocadosource.com/Journals/SAAGA/SAAGA_2022/SAAGA_2022_45_TOC.htm.

Mcleod, A., Hamza, Z., Schoeman, M.H., Moyo, L. & Akinsanmi, O.A., 2024, 'Temporal colonization of macadamia tree roots by *Phytophthora cinnamomi* based on a newly developed quantitative real-time PCR assay', *Plant Pathology* 73, 366-377, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.13819>.

Von Broembsen, S.L. & Brits, G.J., 1985, 'Control of Phytophthora root rot of proteas in South Africa', *Acta Horticulturae* 185, 201-208, <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1986.185.21>.

CON3 Potential impact

Response: Massive (MV)

Confidence: High

Rationale: Phytophthora root rot, caused by *P. cinnamomi*, has the potential to drive species to extinction (McDougall & Liew 2024). In Southwestern Australia (SWA), where *P. cinnamomi* has likely had the greatest impact as an alien invader, the pathogen has been linked to the local extinction of several species and is recognized as one of the primary threats to numerous critically endangered

taxa (McDougall et al. 2024). The Cape Floristic Region (CFR) shares many similarities with SWA in terms of plant family representation, levels of endemism and environmental conditions (Paap et al. 2025, in press). Currently, 97 native species in the CFR are known to be hosts of *P. cinnamomi* (Paap et al. 2025, in press), many of which are already endangered. The most concerning case is that of the critically endangered *Sorocephalus imbricatus*, which has experienced a rapid population decline due to *P. cinnamomi* infection (Paap et al. 2023). As a recalcitrant species with limited regeneration capacity, *S. imbricatus* is now at serious risk of complete extinction, with *P. cinnamomi* likely playing a significant role in its demise.

Once *P. cinnamomi* becomes established at a new site, eradication becomes practically unfeasible (Sena et al. 2018). As a result, the effects of invasion are likely to be permanent, requiring plant communities to adapt. Without appropriate management, *P. cinnamomi* can continue to spread and completely transform environments (Sena et al. 2018). In South Africa, the lack of recognition of *P. cinnamomi* as a serious threat to native flora has resulted in an absence of proper monitoring and management efforts. Consequently, severe impacts may already be unfolding unnoticed.

References:

McDougall, K.L. & Liew, E.C.Y., 2024, 'The susceptibility of rare and threatened NSW species to the root-rot pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*: 2. The identification of species requiring protection or further research', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23106>.

McDougall, K.L., Barrett, S., Velzeboer, R., Cahill, D.M. & Rudman, T., 2024, 'Evaluating the risk to Australia's flora from *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23086>.

Paap, T., Balocchi, F., Wingfield, M.J., 2025, 'The root rot pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*: A long-overlooked threat to the Cape Floristic Region of South Africa', *Biological Invasions*.

Paap, T., Nndanduleni, M. & Wingfield, M.J., 2023, 'A critically endangered Proteaceae in the Cape Floristic Region threatened by an invasive pathogen', *Bothalia-African Biodiversity & Conservation* 53, 1-7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.38201/btha.abc.v53.i1.6>.

Sena, K., Crocker, E., Vincelli, P. & Barton, C., 2018, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* as a driver of forest change: implications for conservation and management', *Forest Ecology and Management* 409, 799–807, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2017.12.022>.

4. Risk Assessment calculations

Likelihood = Probable

Parameter	Likelihood	Stages	Final assessment
LIK1	1	P(entry) = 1	P (invasion) = 1
LIK2	1		
LIK3	1		
LIK4	1	P(establishment) = 1	
LIK5	0.027	P (spread) = 1	
LIK6	1		

Consequence = Massive

Parameter	Mechanism/sector	Response
CON1a	Competition	DD
CON1b	Predation	DD
CON1c	Hybridisation	MC
CON1d	Disease transmission	DD
CON1e	Parasitism	MR
CON1f	Poisoning/toxicity	DD
CON1g	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	DD
CON1h	Grazing/herbivory/browsing	DD
CON1i	Chemical, physical, structural impact	MR
CON1k	Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	MO
CON1	Maximum environmental impact	MR
CON2a	Safety	DD

CON2b	Material and immaterial assets	MO
CON2c	Health	MC
CON2d	Social, spiritual and cultural relations	MN
CON2	Maximum socio-economic impact	MO
CON3	Potential impact	MV

Risk score = High

		Consequence				
		MC	MN	MO	MR	MV
Likelihood	Extremely unlikely	low	low	low	medium	medium
	Very unlikely	low	low	low	medium	high
	Unlikely	low	low	medium	high	high
	Fairly probable	medium	medium	high	high	high
	Probable	medium	high	high	high	high

5. Management

MAN1 What is the feasibility to stop future immigration?	
Response: Low	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is already present in the area (Von Broembsen 1984). Additionally, it is known to occur in two neighbouring countries, Zimbabwe and Eswatini (Rothwell 1982; Von Broembsen 1984), both of which have active border crossings (IOM 2020). The country engages heavily in plant commodity imports (SARS 2025) and receives a high volume of international tourists each year (Statistics South Africa 2024). The risk of importation, therefore, remains high.</p>	
<p>References:</p> <p>IOM (International Organization for Migration), 2020, 'IOM Zimbabwe. 2019 Annual migration flow summary'. Available online: https://dtm.iom.int/dtm_download_track/10348?file=1&type=node&id=8105. Accessed 18 February 2025.</p> <p>Rothwell, A., 1982, 'A revised list of plant diseases occurring in Zimbabwe', <i>Kirkia</i> 12, 233-351, https://www.jstor.org/stable/23502151.</p> <p>SARS, 2025, 'Trade Statistics Data'. Available online: https://tools.sars.gov.za/tradestatsportal/data_download.aspx. Accessed 18 February 2025.</p> <p>Statistics South Africa, 2024, 'Natural Capital Series 5: Experimental Biodiversity-Based Tourism Estimates for South Africa, 2013 to 2019.', <i>Discussion document D0401.5. Produced in collaboration with the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) and the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE). Statistics South Africa, Pretoria.</i>, https://www.statssa.gov.za/?page_id=1854&PPN=D0401.5&SCH=73953.</p> <p>Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Occurrence of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> on indigenous and exotic hosts in South Africa, with special reference to the South-Western Cape Province', <i>Phytophylactica</i> 16, 221-226, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_873.</p>	

MAN2 Benefits of the Taxon					
MAN2a Socio-economic benefits of the Taxon					
Benefit	Magnitude	Current?	Replaceability	Stakeholders	Confidence
<p>Rationale: There are no benefits to justify permit issuing for <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> (i.e., there is no context where it would be 'desirable' to allow the introduction of <i>P. cinnamomi</i>), and there are no foreseeable conflicts of interest in managing <i>P. cinnamomi</i> disease.</p>					
References:					
MAN2b Environmental benefits of the Taxon					
Benefit	Magnitude	Current?	Replaceability	Stakeholders	Confidence

<p>Rationale: There are no environmental benefits that justify issuing permits for <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>. <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> is pathogenic to some alien plant species present in South Africa (Appendix 1). Furthermore, it has been found causing mortality on alien and invasive <i>Banksia</i> species, limiting their invasiveness at infested sites in the Cape Floristic Region (Qongqo et al. 2022). However, there are also some highly invasive <i>Banksia</i> species that exhibit anti-microbial activity and show resistance to infection (Qongqo et al. 2022). These species have a competitive advantage over susceptible taxa, which may facilitate their invasion.</p>					
<p>References: Qongqo, A., Nchu, F. & Geerts, S., 2022, 'Relationship of alien species continues in a foreign land: The case of <i>Phytophthora</i> and Australian <i>Banksia</i> (Proteaceae) in South African Fynbos', <i>Ecology and Evolution</i> 12, https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.9100.</p>					

MAN3 Can the risk be reduced?	
Response: No	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale: The answer is set to 'No' as per the framework. The issuing of permits, exemptions or prohibitions cannot reduce the risk of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> to acceptable levels. In addition, <i>P. cinnamomi</i> doesn't provide any benefits, and thus, there are no contexts in which the introduction or maintenance of the pathogen would be desirable.</p> <p>However, the risk of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> to South African natural areas and its impact can be mitigated. Certain restrictions could help protect high-risk areas (e.g., the natural range of highly localised/endemic critically endangered taxa). These include restricting plant material and soil movement into conservation areas (or certifying disease-free providers) and preventing orchards or plantations from being established in direct proximity to them; enforcing high biosecurity and hygiene standards for visitors entering protected areas (e.g., boot sanitization stations at hiking access points) and for nurseries supplying plants for restoration or urban planting projects (e.g., testing for <i>P. cinnamomi</i> and certifying <i>P. cinnamomi</i> -free providers; SANBI & FABI 2025); and issuing permits for phosphite use as a <i>P. cinnamomi</i> preventative treatment in high-risk areas (e.g., highly susceptible endangered taxa near infested sites) and as a curative treatment to prolong plant survival and support germplasm collections to further aid conservation efforts (Barrett et al. 2024).</p> <p>Paap et al. (2025) propose a comprehensive programme to investigate and manage <i>P. cinnamomi</i> in vulnerable areas, highlighting several components that would directly inform the conservation strategies required to mitigate the impacts of <i>P. cinnamomi</i>. These include: (i) raising awareness of the threat of <i>P. cinnamomi</i>, (ii) training relevant stakeholders to identify disease symptoms (Nndanduleni et al. 2023) and in biosecurity and hygiene best practices (SANBI & FABI 2025), (iii) monitoring conservation areas with trained personnel, (iv) assess <i>P. cinnamomi</i>'s current spread and disease prevalence in the field, (v) assess the susceptibility of endangered taxa to prioritize conservation efforts, and (vi) develop phosphite application protocols.</p> <p>Many of the suggested measures to reduce <i>P. cinnamomi</i>'s risk to natural vegetation are also relevant for reducing the spread and mitigating the impact of a wide range of invasive pests and pathogens. Strengthening biosecurity standards to address the threat of invasive pests and pathogens is essential for mitigating their impact.</p>	
<p>References: Barrett, S., Yates, C.J., Dillon, R., Dilly, M., Varcoe, B., Martin, D., et al., 2024, 'Mitigation of disease and browsing impacts, and translocation, supports post-fire threatened flora recovery', <i>Australian Journal of Botany</i> 72, https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23081. Nndanduleni, M., Wondafrash, M., Gabayi, M. & Paap, T., 2021, 'Battle to save iconic silver trees', <i>Veld & Flora</i> 107, 38-43, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/ejc-veld_v107_n1_a14. Paap, T., Balocchi, F., Wingfield, M.J., 2025, 'The root rot pathogen <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>: A long-overlooked threat to the Cape Floristic Region of South Africa', <i>Biological Invasions</i>, <i>In press</i>. SANBI & FABI, 2025, 'Biosecurity in living plant collections in South Africa—guidelines for best practice'. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Kirstenbosch and Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute, University of Pretoria. <i>In press</i>.</p>	
MAN3a Do some entities of the Taxon pose a reduced risk?	
Response: No	Confidence: High

<p>Rationale: <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> has no recognized subspecies, but isolates of different mating types (~sexes) may have distinct preferences for specific environments and hosts. Mating type A2 is generally more invasive globally than A1 (Arentz 2017); however, both types are present in South Africa, and both pose a threat to native flora (Engelbrecht et al. 2022).</p>	
<p>References: Arentz, F., 2017, '<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> A1: An ancient resident of New Guinea and Australia of Gondwanan origin?', <i>Forest Pathology</i> 47, e12342, https://doi.org/10.1111/efp.12342. Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', <i>Phytopathology</i> 112, 1568-1574, https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-10-21-0414-R.</p>	
<p>MAN3b Is the risk of the Taxon reduced under certain environmental conditions?</p>	
Response: No	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale: While environmental conditions significantly influence <i>P. cinnamomi</i>'s ability to establish and infect plants (e.g., areas with rainfall < 400 mm/year and/or with calcareous soils are at lower risk of invasion; see LIK4), the issue of permits is not applicable for management of <i>P. cinnamomi</i>, as this microorganism is most often moved unintentionally (Migliorini et al. 2015) and provides no appreciable benefits.</p> <p>Prohibiting the introduction of plant material and soil to conservation areas (with the option of biosecurity certification) would help protect the natural vegetation from <i>P. cinnamomi</i>, as well as other invasive pests and pathogens (Migliorini et al. 2015). Additionally, minimising the establishment of orchards or plantations (especially of known <i>P. cinnamomi</i> hosts) close to high-risk conservation areas can further safeguard these environments (Serrano et al. 2019).</p>	
<p>References: Migliorini, D., Ghelardini, L., Tondini, E., Luchi, N. & Santini, A., 2015, 'The potential of symptomless potted plants for carrying invasive soilborne plant pathogens', <i>Diversity and Distributions</i> 21, 1218-1229, https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12347. Serrano, M.S., Osmundson, T., Almaraz-Sánchez, A., Croucher, P.J.P., Swiecki, T., Alvarado-Rosales, D. & Garbelotto, M., 2019, 'A microsatellite analysis used to identify global pathways of movement of <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> and the likely sources of wildland infestations in California and Mexico', <i>Phytopathology</i> 109, 1577-1593, https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-03-19-0102-R.</p>	
<p>MAN3c Can containment options reduce the risk of the Taxon?</p>	
Response: No	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale: The answer is set to 'No', as the issuing of permits is not an effective tool for <i>P. cinnamomi</i> management and there are no benefits associated to it. The issuing of restrictions or special permits to enforce better biosecurity and hygiene standards for certain activities can help reduce the risks of <i>P. cinnamomi</i> (and other invasive pests and pathogens) being introduced into new areas, however, there is not an 'acceptable level' that can be reached.</p> <p>Nurseries can serve as a hub for dissemination of a wide range of plant pathogens including <i>P. cinnamomi</i>, as they offer optimum conditions for their growth and proliferation (Pautasso et al. 2015, Frankel et al. 2020, Laurence et al. 2024). Restrictions or special permits could be issued for nurseries engaged in restoration activities or urban greening projects in proximity to conservation high risk areas. Hygiene measures can be required for visitors/working staff at access points of conservation areas, both at infested and disease-free sites (Liew et al. 2023). Similar measures can be implemented for vehicles accessing these areas (McDougall & Liew 2024). Because <i>P. cinnamomi</i> is not visually detectable and may require laboratory sampling and processing for identification, its containment largely depends on adhering to biosecurity and hygiene best practices, as required for any pathogenic microorganism.</p>	
<p>References: Frankel, S.J., Conforti, C., Hillman, J., Ingolia, M., Shor, A., Benner, D., et al., 2020, '<i>Phytophthora</i> introductions in restoration areas: Responding to protect California native flora from human-assisted pathogen spread', <i>Forests</i> 11, 1291, https://doi.org/10.3390/f11121291. Laurence, M.H., Mertin, A.A., Scarlett, K., Pang, C., Tabassum, S., Leishman, M.R., et al., 2024, '<i>Phytophthora</i> in urban tree planting stock: Are we managing the risk to the urban forest and natural ecosystems?', <i>Plant Pathology</i> 00, 1-13, https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.13960.</p>	

Liew, E.C., Phelan, M. & McDougall, K.L., 2023, 'The efficacy of a range of hygiene measures for boot cleaning to protect natural vegetation from *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Scientific Reports* 13, 5825, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-32681-7>.
 McDougall, K. & Liew, E., 2024, 'Dispersal of *Phytophthora* species by off-road vehicles in New South Wales', *Australasian Plant Pathology* 53, 63-65, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13313-023-00961-5>.
 Pautasso, M., Schlegel, M. & Holdenrieder, O., 2015, 'Forest health in a changing world', *Microbial Ecology* 69, 826-842, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-014-0545-8>.

MAN3d Is management in place that can reduce the invasion or impact of the Taxon?

Response: No

Confidence: High

Rationale: There is no biocontrol agent available for controlling *Phytophthora cinnamomi* as an invasive pathogen. Biological control products, derived from fungi or bacteria, are available for managing plant diseases in specific settings, such as greenhouses and nurseries. However, these products are non-specific and do not establish or spread independently requiring continuous application (ill-suited to field settings).

No other management measures are in place that passively reduce the invasion risk or impact of *P. cinnamomi* in natural environments of South Africa. Agricultural producers, particularly avocado growers, have invested significant resources in breeding disease-resistant rootstocks and developing disease management schemes (Douhan et al. 2011; Jordaan et al. 2022). However, these practices face additional challenges when applied to native species (Nndanduleni et al. 2021). Managing *P. cinnamomi* in natural areas requires a plan that integrates targeted strategies with high biosecurity standards (Paap et al. 2025). Strengthening biosecurity measures at conservation areas, nurseries providing plants for restoration and urban plantings, and actively engaging with plant health experts for monitoring and diagnosis (SANBI & FABI 2025), can all significantly reduce the risk of spread of *P. cinnamomi*. When these activities are consistently implemented, they also serve as passive management for many other invasive pathogens and pests.

Risks to vulnerable species can also be mitigated by enhancing conservation activities, including germplasm collection for endangered taxa and/or establishing ex-situ collections (Paap et al. 2025). These activities also assist with meeting South Africa's Strategy for Plant Conservation (NSPC) targets (Raimondo 2015). In addition, testing the susceptibility of native species to *P. cinnamomi* can assist in prioritization of conservation efforts, and the application of phosphite can reduce its impact in field (Barrett et al. 2024; Paap et al. 2025).

References:

Barrett, S., Yates, C.J., Dillon, R., Dilly, M., Varcoe, B., Martin, D., et al., 2024, 'Mitigation of disease and browsing impacts, and translocation, supports post-fire threatened flora recovery', *Australian Journal of Botany* 72, <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23081>.
 Douhan, G.W., Fuller, E., Mckee, B. & Pond, E., 2011, 'Genetic diversity analysis of avocado (*Persea americana* Miller) rootstocks selected under greenhouse conditions for tolerance to phytophthora root rot caused by *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Euphytica* 182, 209-217, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-011-0433-y>.
 Jordaan, E., Anelich, R. & Denner, F., 2022, 'Supporting crop establishment and trees in established avocado orchards, by way of combined use of biological and chemical solutions', *South African avocado growers association yearbook* 45, 24-37, https://www.avocadosource.com/Journals/SAAGA/SAAGA_2022/SAAGA_2022_45_TOC.htm.
 Nndanduleni, M., Wondafrash, M., Gabayi, M. & Paap, T., 2021, 'Battle to save iconic silver trees', *Veld & Flora* 107, 38-43, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/ejc-veld_v107_n1_a14.
 Paap, T., Balocchi, F., Wingfield, M.J., 2025, 'The root rot pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*: A long-overlooked threat to the Cape Floristic Region of South Africa', *Biological Invasions*, *In press*.
 Raimondo, D., 2015, 'South Africa's Strategy for Plant Conservation', South African National Biodiversity Institute and the Botanical Society of South Africa, Pretoria.
 SANBI & FABI, 2025, 'Biosecurity in living plant collections in South Africa—guidelines for best practice', South African National Biodiversity Institute, Kirstenbosch and Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute, University of Pretoria. *In press*.

MAN4 Should eradication be considered as a management goal?

Response: No

Confidence: High

Rationale: *Phytophthora cinnamomi* was first detected in South Africa almost 100 years ago (Wager 1931, 1941). It has become widespread in the country (Appendix BAC10) and currently has a large

list of known alien and native hosts (Appendix 1). Eradication of *P. cinnamomi* from South Africa under the current context is unfeasible. While spot eradication and containment of disease fronts has been accomplished in Australia by means of chemical fumigants (Metam-sodium) and fallow soil treatments (Dunstan et al. 2010; Dunstan et al. 2020), these methods are not applicable in every context or at large scale. Effective management in South Africa should rather focus on containment and minimising impacts.

References:

- Dunstan, W.A., Howard, K., Grigg, A., Shaw, C., Burgess, T.I. & Hardy, G.E.S.J., 2020, 'Towards eradication of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* using a fallow approach in a mediterranean climate', *Forests* 11, 1101, <https://doi.org/10.3390/f11101101>.
- Dunstan, W.A., Rudman, T., Shearer, B.L., Moore, N.A., Paap, T., Calver, M.C., et al., 2010, 'Containment and spot eradication of a highly destructive, invasive plant pathogen (*Phytophthora cinnamomi*) in natural ecosystems', *Biological Invasions* 12, 913-925, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-009-9512-6>.
- Wager, V.A., 1931, 'Diseases of plants in South Africa due to members of the *Pythiaceae*', *Union of South Africa, Dept. Agric. Sci. Bull.* 105, 43
- Wager, V.A., 1941, 'Descriptions of the South African *Pythiaceae* with records of their occurrence', *Bothalia* 4, 3-35, <https://journals.abcjournal.aosis.co.za/index.php/abc/article/view/1708/1673>.

6. Recommendations

REC1 What are the options for regulation of the *Taxon*?

Options for regulation: Retain current listing as 1b

Rationale: *Phytophthora cinnamomi* is a highly invasive microbial plant pathogen of high risk to South African native flora. The pathogen was first detected in the country almost 100 years ago, and a large number of native hosts have been discovered since. Based on isolated independent studies it has become evident that *P. cinnamomi* is widespread in the country, and causing death of numerous native taxa, however, the full extent of it's invasion and realized impacts is still not fully understood.

Since 2014, *P. cinnamomi* has been listed as Category 1b. This is appropriate since listing as Category 1a is not applicable as eradication is not feasible. Listing as Category 1b with exemptions or prohibitions, or Category 2 are not appropriate options either, since *P. cinnamomi* (i) is high risk, (ii) it does not produce any environmental or socio-economic benefits, and (iii) there is no applicability in issuing permits.

Nevertheless, the listing of *P. cinnamomi* as an alien invasive species did not translate into any actions or regulations, and the pathogen was left unmanaged. Following this risk analysis, an Invasive Species Management Programme needs to be developed (Wilson & Kumschick, 2024; Paap et al., 2025) to make meaningful progress toward mitigating the impacts and risks posed by this aggressive plant pathogen.

Recommendation: Retain current listing as 1b

References:

- Paap, T., Balocchi, F., Wingfield, M.J., 2025, 'The root rot pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*: A long-overlooked threat to the Cape Floristic Region of South Africa', *Biological Invasions*, *In press*.
- Wilson, J.R.U., Kumschick, S., 2024, 'The regulation of alien species in South Africa', *South African Journal of Science*, 120(5/6). <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2024/17002>

Appendix BAC7 (native range of the Taxon):

Representation of the theoretical geographical centre of origin of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. Based on Shakya et al. 2021 (Shakya, S.K., Grünwald, N.J., Fieland, V.J., Knaus, B.J., Weiland, J.E., Maia, C., et al., 2021, 'Phylogeography of the wide-host range panglobal plant pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Molecular Ecology* 30, 5164-5178, <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16109>).

Appendix BAC8 (global alien range of the Taxon):

Representation of geographical distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* worldwide. Based on: European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO) (2022) EPPO Global Database (available online). <https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/PHYTCN/distribution>. Access date: February 20th, 2022; and Shakya, S.K., Grünwald, N.J., Fieland, V.J., Knaus, B.J., Weiland, J.E., Maia, C., et al., 2021, 'Phylogeography of the wide-host range panglobal plant pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Molecular Ecology* 30, 5164-5178, <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16109>.

Appendix BAC10 (range of the Taxon in the Area):

Geographical distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in South Africa. Map built using QGIS Desktop 3.32.2 based on waypoints available in literature and isolates deposited in the culture collection (CMW) of the Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI), University of Pretoria.

References:

- Bose, T., Wingfield, M.J., Roux, J., Vivas, M. & Burgess, T.I., 2018, 'Community composition and distribution of *Phytophthora* species across adjacent native and non-native forests of South Africa', *Fungal Ecology* 36, 17-25, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2018.09.001>.
- Maseko, B.O., 2010, 'Die-back of cold tolerant *Eucalyptus* associated with *Phytophthora* spp. in South Africa', PhD Thesis, University of Pretoria, Pretoria. <https://upetd.up.ac.za/handle/2263/29415?show=full>.
- Migliorini, D., Vivas, M., Wingfield, M.J., Shaw, C. & Burgess, T.I., 2023, 'Oomycete composition in Proteaceae orchards and natural stands on three continents', *Mycological Progress* 22, 75, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-023-01925-1>.
- Nesamari, R., Coutinho, T.A. & Roux, J., 2017, 'Investigations into *Encephalartos* insect pests and diseases in South Africa and identification of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* as a pathogen of the Modjadji cycad', *Plant Pathology* 66, 612-622, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.12619>.
- Oh, E., Gryzenhout, M., Wingfield, B.D., Wingfield, M.J. & Burgess, T.I., 2013, 'Surveys of soil and water reveal a goldmine of *Phytophthora* diversity in South African natural ecosystems', *IMA fungus* 4, 123-131, <https://doi.org/10.5598/imafungus.2013.04.01.12>.
- Paap, T., Nndanduleni, M. & Wingfield, M.J., 2023, 'A critically endangered Proteaceae in the Cape Floristic Region threatened by an invasive pathogen', *Bothalia-African Biodiversity & Conservation* 53, 1-7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.38201/btha.abc.v53.i1.6>.
- Wager, V.A., 1931, 'Diseases of plants in South Africa due to members of the *Pythiaceae*', *Union of South Africa, Dept. Agric. Sci. Bull.* 105, 43

Appendix 1: List of recorded *Phytophthora cinnamomi* hosts in South Africa.

Table 1. General statistics of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* hosts recorded in South Africa. –

Taxon level/type	n records
General	
Families	23
Genera	46
Species	145
Sub-Species	11
South African	
Endemic	93
Native (not endemic)	7

Table 2. Host records for *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in South Africa (e = endemic, ne = not endemic).

Family	Genus	Species	Synonym	Status SA	Origin (if alien)	First reference in SA
Araucariaceae	<i>Araucaria</i>	<i>angustifolia</i>		Alien	Brazil	Von Broembsen (1984)
Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea</i>	sp.		Alien	Undetermined	Von Broembsen (1984)
Bromeliaceae	<i>Ananas</i>	<i>comosus</i>		Alien	Central and South America	Gorter (1977)
Bruniaceae	<i>Berzelia</i>	<i>intermedia</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Casuarinaceae	<i>Casuarina</i>	<i>cunninghamiana</i>		Alien	Australia	Crous et al. (2000)
Cupressaceae	<i>Chamaecyparis</i>	<i>lawsoniana</i>		Alien	North America	Von Broembsen (1984)
Cupressaceae	<i>Thuja</i>	<i>occidentalis</i>	<i>T. nana</i> var <i>compacta</i>	Alien	USA	Von Broembsen (1984)
Cupressaceae	<i>Widdringtonia</i>	<i>cedarbergensis</i>	<i>W. wallichii</i>	Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Cupressaceae	<i>Widdringtonia</i>	<i>nodiflora</i>	<i>W. cupressoides</i>	Native (ne)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Cupressaceae	<i>Widdringtonia</i>	<i>schwarzii</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Curtisiaceae	<i>Curtisia</i>	<i>dentata</i>		Native (ne)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Cyatheaceae	<i>Gymnosphaera</i>	<i>capensis</i>		Native (ne)		Unpublished data.
Ericaceae	<i>Erica</i>	<i>baccans</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Ericaceae	<i>Erica</i>	<i>blenna</i>		Native (e)		Van der Merwe & Van Wyk (1973)
Ericaceae	<i>Erica</i>	<i>oatesii</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Ericaceae	<i>Erica</i>	<i>patersonia</i>	<i>E. patersonii</i>	Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Ericaceae	<i>Erica</i>	<i>plukenetii</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Ericaceae	<i>Erica</i>	sp.		Undetermined		Van der Merwe & Van Wyk (1973); Von Broembsen (1984)
Ericaceae	<i>Rhododendron</i>	<i>dichroanthum</i> X <i>wardii</i> (cv <i>Tidbit</i>)		Alien	Asia	Von Broembsen (1984)

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Fabaceae	<i>Liparia</i>	sp.	<i>Priestleya</i>	Native		Von Broembsen (1984)
Fagaceae	<i>Castanea</i>	<i>sativa</i>		Alien	Europe (Southeastern) - Asia	Gorter (1977)
Fagaceae	<i>Quercus</i>	<i>cerris</i>		Alien	Europe, Middle East	Oh et al. (2011)
Lauraceae	<i>Ocotea</i>	<i>bullata</i>		Native (e)		Lübbe and Geldenhuys (1990); Lübbe (1991)
Lauraceae	<i>Persea</i>	<i>americana</i>		Alien	Central America	Wager (1931); Wager (1941)
Meliaceae	<i>Nymanina</i>	<i>capensis</i>		Native (ne)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Moraceae	<i>Ficus</i>	<i>macrophylla</i>		Alien	Australia	Engelbretch et al. (2022)
Myrtaceae	<i>Corymbia</i>	<i>citriodora</i>	<i>Eucalyptus citriodora</i>	Alien	Australia	Lundquist & Baxter (1985)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>cloeziana</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>fastigata</i>		Alien	Australia	Lundquist & Baxter (1985)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>fraxinoides</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>grandis</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>lehmannii</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>macarthurii</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>radiata</i>		Alien	Australia	Lundquist & Baxter (1985)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>saligna</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	<i>smithii</i>		Alien	Australia	Linde et al. (1999)
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	sp.		Alien	Undetermined	Von Broembsen (1984)
Pinaceae	<i>Cedrus</i>	<i>deodara</i>		Alien	South Asia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus</i>	<i>clausa</i>		Alien	USA	Lundquist (1986)
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus</i>	<i>elliottii</i>		Alien	USA	Lundquist (1987a)
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus</i>	<i>halepensis</i>		Alien	Europe, Northern Africa, Middle East	Lundquist (1987a)
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus</i>	<i>patula</i>		Alien	Mexico	Von Broembsen (1984)
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus</i>	<i>pinaster</i>		Alien	Europe, Northern Africa	Lundquist (1987a)
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus</i>	<i>radiata</i>		Alien	USA	Lundquist (1986)
Podocarpaceae	<i>Podocarpus</i>	<i>latifolius</i>		Native (ne)		Engelbretch et al. (2022)
Primulaceae	<i>Myrsine</i>	<i>melanophloeos</i>		Native (ne)		Balocchi et al. Unpublished
Proteaceae	<i>Aulax</i>	<i>cancellata</i>	<i>A. pinifolia</i>	Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Aulax</i>	<i>pallasia</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>baxteri</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>burdettii</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)

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Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>coccinea</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>ericifolia</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>formosa</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>hookeriana</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>integrifolia</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>menziesii</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>prionotes</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>serrata</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>speciosa</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Banksia</i>	<i>spinulosa</i>		Alien	Australia	Qongqo et al. (2022)
Proteaceae	<i>Brabejum</i>	<i>stellatifolium</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Hakea</i>	<i>sericea</i>	<i>H. acicularis</i>	Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>album</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>argenteum</i>		Native (e)		Van Wyk (1973)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>comosum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>daphnoides</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>discolor</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985); Raabe (1978)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>galpinii</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>gandogeri</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>laureolum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>loranthifolium</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>meridianum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>microcephalum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>nobile</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>orientale</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>pubescens</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>rubrum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>salicifolium</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)

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Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>salignum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	sp.		Undetermined		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>spissifolium</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>tinctum</i>		Native (e)		Van Wyk (1973); Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>tradouwense</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>uliginosum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984); Von Broembsen & Brits (1985)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucadendron</i>	<i>xanthoconus</i>		Native (e)		Benic (1986)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	× <i>cordifolium-lineare</i>		Native (h)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	× <i>cordifolium-tottum</i>		Native (h)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>catherinae</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>conocarpodendron</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>cordifolium</i>		Native (e)		Van Wyk (1973)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>cordifolium</i> cv. gold dust		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>cuneiforme</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>erubescens</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>formosum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>fulgens</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>glabrum</i>		Native (e)		Van Wyk (1973)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>grandiflorum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>lineare</i>		Native (e)		Van Wyk (1973)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>muirii</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>mundii</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>patersonii</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>pluridens</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>praecox</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>praemorsum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>prostratum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>reflexum</i>	<i>Leucadendron</i>	Native (e)		Van Wyk (1973); Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	sp.		Native		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>tomentosum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>tottum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)

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Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>truncatulum</i>	<i>L. truncatum</i>	Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>utriculosum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Leucospermum</i>	<i>vestitum</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Macadamia</i>	sp.		Alien		McLeod et al. (2024)
Proteaceae	<i>Mimetes</i>	<i>argenteus</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Mimetes</i>	<i>capitulatus</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Mimetes</i>	<i>cucullatus</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Mimetes</i>	<i>hirtus</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Mimetes</i>	<i>hottentoticus</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Mimetes</i>	<i>splendidus</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Orothamnus</i>	<i>zeyheri</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Paranomus</i>	<i>reflexus</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>aurea</i>	<i>P. longiflora</i>	Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>burchellii</i>		Native (e)		Knox-Davies et al. (1987)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>cynaroides</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>effusa</i>	<i>P. marlothii</i>	Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>eximia</i>		Native (e)		Knox-Davies et al. (1987)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>grandiceps</i>		Native (e)		Knox-Davies et al. (1987)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>lanceolata</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>laurifolia</i>		Native (e)		Knox-Davies et al. (1987)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>lepidocarpodendron</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>longifolia</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>lorifolia</i>		Native (e)		Knox-Davies et al. (1987)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>magnifica</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>mundii</i>		Native (e)		Knox-Davies et al. (1987)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>nana</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>neriifolia</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>nitida</i>	<i>P. arborea</i>	Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>obtusifolia</i>		Native (e)		Raabe (1978)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>punctata</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>repens</i>		Native (e)		Knox-Davies et al. (1987)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>roupelliae</i>		Native (ne)		Von Broembsen (1984)

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Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	sp.		Native		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Protea</i>	<i>susannae</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Serruria</i>	<i>florida</i>		Native (e)		Crous et al. (2000)
Proteaceae	<i>Serruria</i>	<i>kraussii</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Proteaceae	<i>Sorocephalus</i>	<i>imbricatus</i>		Native (e)		Paap et al. (2023)
Proteaceae	<i>Telopea</i>	<i>speciosissima</i>		Alien	Australia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Rosaceae	<i>Cliffortia</i>	<i>grandifolia</i>		Native (e)		Von Broembsen (1984)
Rosaceae	<i>Prunus</i>	<i>persica</i>		Alien	China	Crous et al. (2000)
Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus</i>	<i>communis</i>		Alien	Europe, Asia	Von Broembsen (1984)
Rutaceae	<i>Agathosma</i>	<i>betulina</i>		Native (e)		Bezuidenhout et al. (2010)
Rutaceae	<i>Agathosma</i>	<i>crenulata</i>		Native (e)		Bezuidenhout et al. (2010)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	<i>rupestris</i>		Alien	USA	Von Broembsen (1984)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	<i>rupestris</i> (cv. Rupestris du Lot)		Alien	USA	Van der Merwe et al. (1972)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	<i>rupestris</i> (cv. St. George)		Alien	USA	Von Broembsen (1984)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	<i>rupestris</i> cv. Constantia Metallica		Alien	USA	Von Broembsen (1984)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	<i>rupestris</i> × <i>berlandieri</i> Pl. cv. 'Richter 110'		Alien	USA, Mexico	Van der Merwe et al. (1972)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	<i>rupestris</i> × <i>berlandieri</i> Pl. cv. 'Richter 99'		Alien	USA, Mexico	Van der Merwe et al. (1972)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	<i>rupestris</i> × <i>riparia</i> Mich. cv. '110-14 Mgt'		Alien	North America	Von Broembsen (1984)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	sp.		Alien		Von Broembsen (1984)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	<i>vinifera</i>		Alien	Europe, Asia	Oudemans & Coffey (1991)
Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i>	× <i>champini</i> (cv. Ramsey = Salt Creek)		Alien	USA	Von Broembsen (1984)
Zamiaceae	<i>Encephalartos</i>	<i>transvenosus</i>		Native (e)		Nesamari et al. (2017)

References:

- Benic, L., 1986, 'Pathological problems associated with propagation material in protea nurseries in South Africa', *Acta Horticulturae* 185, 229-236, <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1986.185.24>.
- Bezuidenhout, C., Denman, S., Kirk, S., Botha, W., Mostert, L. & Mcleod, A., 2010, '*Phytophthora* taxa associated with cultivated *Agathosma*, with emphasis on the *P. citricola* complex and *P. capensis* sp. nov', *Persoonia-Molecular Phylogeny and Evolution of Fungi* 25, 32-49, <https://doi.org/10.3767/003158510X538371>.
- Crous, P.W., Phillips, A.J.L. & Baxter, A.P., 2000. 'Phytopathogenic Fungi from South Africa.', University of Stellenbosch, Department of Plant Pathology Press Stellenbosch, South Africa. 358 pp.
- Engelbrecht, J., Duong, T.A., Paap, T., Hubert, J.M., Hanneman, J.J. & Van Den Berg, N., 2022, 'Population genetic analyses of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* reveals three lineages and movement between natural vegetation and avocado orchards in South Africa', *Phytopathology* 112, 1568-1574, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-10-21-0414-R>.

- Gorter, G.J.M.A., 1977, 'Index of plant pathogens and the diseases they cause in cultivated plants in South Africa.', *Republic South Africa Dept. Agric. Techn. Serv. Pl. Protect. Res. Inst. Sci. Bull.* 392, 1-177
- Knox-Davies, P.S., Van Wyk, P.S. & Marasas, W.F.O., 1987, 'Diseases of *Protea*, *Leucospermum* and *Leucadendron* recorded in South Africa', *Phytophylactica* 19, 327-338, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_1101.
- Linde, C., Kemp, G.H. & Wingfield, M.J., 1999, 'Variation in pathogenicity among South African isolates of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 105, 231-239, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008780429770>.
- Lübbe, W., 1991, 'The response of *Ocotea bullata* (Lauraceae) to flooded conditions', *South African Forestry Journal* 157, 32-37, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00382167.1991.9629097>.
- Lübbe, W.A. & Geldenhuys, C.J., 1990, 'Decline and mortality of *Ocotea bullata* trees in the southern Cape forests', *South African Forestry Journal* 154, 7-14, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00382167.1990.9629044>.
- Lundquist, J., 1986, 'Fungi Associated with Pinus in South Africa Part I. The Transvaal', *South African Forestry Journal* 138, 1-14, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00382167.1986.9630036>.
- Lundquist, J., 1987a, 'Fungi associated with Pinus in South Africa. Part II. The Cape', *South African Forestry Journal* 140, 4-15, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00382167.1987.9630063>.
- Lundquist, J., 1987b, 'Fungi associated with *Pinus* in South Africa, Part III, Natal, the Orange Free State and the Republic of Transkei', *South African Forestry Journal* 143, 11-19, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00382167.1987.9630295>.
- Lundquist, J.E. & Baxter, A.P., 1985, 'Fungi associated with *Eucalyptus* in South Africa', *South African Forestry Journal* 135, 9-19, <https://doi.org/uplib.idm.oclc.org/10.1080/00382167.1985.9629602>.
- Mcleod, A., Hamza, Z., Schoeman, M.H., Moyo, L. & Akinsanmi, O.A., 2024, 'Temporal colonization of macadamia tree roots by *Phytophthora cinnamomi* based on a newly developed quantitative real-time PCR assay', *Plant Pathology* 73, 366-377, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.13819>.
- Nesamari, R., Coutinho, T.A. & Roux, J., 2017, 'Investigations into *Encephalartos* insect pests and diseases in South Africa and identification of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* as a pathogen of the Modjadji cycad', *Plant Pathology* 66, 612-622, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.12619>.
- Oh, E., Wingfield, B.D., Wingfield, M.J. & Roux, J., 2011, 'First report of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* associated with stem cankers of *Quercus cerris* in South Africa', *New Disease Reports* 24, 2044-0588.2011, <https://doi.org/10.5197/j.2044-0588.2011.024.011>.
- Oudemans, P. & Coffey, M.D., 1991, 'Isozyme comparison within and among worldwide sources of three morphologically distinct species of *Phytophthora*', *Mycological Research* 95, 19-30, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0953-7562\(09\)81358-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0953-7562(09)81358-0).
- Paap, T., Nndanduleni, M. & Wingfield, M.J., 2023, 'A critically endangered Proteaceae in the Cape Floristic Region threatened by an invasive pathogen', *Bothalia-African Biodiversity & Conservation* 53, 1-7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.38201/btha.abc.v53.i1.6>.
- Qongqo, A., Nchu, F. & Geerts, S., 2022, 'Relationship of alien species continues in a foreign land: The case of *Phytophthora* and Australian *Banksia* (Proteaceae) in South African Fynbos', *Ecology and Evolution* 12, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.9100>.
- Raabe, R.D., 1978, 'Susceptibility of some Proteaceae to *Phytophthora cinnamomi* and *Pythium vexans*', *Plant Disease Reporter* 62, 888-889, <https://hdl.handle.net/2027/chi.23661252?urlappend=%3Bseq=350%3Bownerid=13510798901326607-420>.
- Van Der Merwe, J.J.H., Joubert, D.J. & Matthee, F.N., 1972, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* root rot of grape-vines in the western Cape', *Phytophylactica* 4, 133-136, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_323.
- Van Der Merwe, J.J.H. & Van Wyk, P.S., 1973, 'Hosts of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in the Western Cape Province of South Africa', *Plant Disease Reporter* 57, 1005-1006, https://books.google.co.za/books?id=8aokoOcOBHoC&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false.
- Van Wyk, P.S., 1973, 'Root and crown rot of silver trees', *Journal of South African Botany* 39, 255-260, <https://archive.org/details/biostor-288929>.
- Von Broembsen, S.L., 1984, 'Occurrence of *Phytophthora cinnamomi* on indigenous and exotic hosts in South Africa, with special reference to the South-Western Cape Province', *Phytophylactica* 16, 221-226, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA03701263_873.
- Von Broembsen, S.L. & Brits, G., 1985, 'Phytophthora root rot of commercially cultivated proteas in South Africa', *Plant Disease* 69, 211-213, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-69-211>.
- Von Broembsen, S.L. & Kruger, F.J., 1985, '*Phytophthora cinnamomi* associated with mortality of native vegetation in South Africa', *Plant Disease* 69, 715-717, <https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-69-715>.
- Wager, V.A., 1931, 'Diseases of plants in South Africa due to members of the *Pythiaceae*', *Union of South Africa, Dept. Agric. Sci. Bull.* 105, 43
- Wager, V.A., 1941, 'Descriptions of the South African *Pythiaceae* with records of their occurrence', *Bothalia* 4, 3-35, <https://journals.abcjournal.aosis.co.za/index.php/abc/article/view/1708/1673>.

Appendix 2: Köppen-Geiger climate classification map of South Africa. Climates favourable for *Phytophthora cinnamomi* are in colours. Built based on the updated 1-km resolution 1991-2020 timeframe developed by Beck et al. (2023).

Map built using QGIS Desktop 3.32.2.

References and shapefile sources:

Beck, H.E., McVicar, T.R., Vergopolan, N., Berg, A., Lutsko, N.J., Dufour, A., Zeng, Z., Jiang, X., van Dijk, A.I.J.M., Miralles, D.G., 2023, 'High-resolution (1 km) Köppen-Geiger maps for 1901–2099 based on constrained CMIP6 projections' *Scientific Data*, 10,724.

Appendix 3:

Rainfall areas (annual average) map of South Africa.

Constructed from 40-year (1981-2020) average map from SASSCAL (2021).

Map built using QGIS Desktop 3.32.2.

References and shapefile sources:

SASSCAL (Southern African Science Service Centre for Climate Change and Adaptive Land Management), 2021, 'Average annual, 40-year average & annual precipitation totals SADC countries from 1981 to 2020', SASSCAL Data and Information Portal.

Appendix 4: CLIMEX models for *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in South Africa. Extracted and compiled from Burgess et al. (2017).

References:

Brasier, C.M. & Scott, J.K., 1994, 'European oak declines and global warming: a theoretical assessment with special reference to the activity of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*', *Eppo Bulletin* 24, 221-232, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2338.1994.tb01063.x>.

Burgess, T.I., Scott, J.K., McDougall, K.L., Stukely, M.J., Crane, C., Dunstan, W.A., et al., 2017, 'Current and projected global distribution of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, one of the world's worst plant pathogens', *Global Change Biology* 23, 1661-1674, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13492>.

Desprez-Loustau, M.-L., Robin, C., Reynaud, G., Déqué, M., Badeau, V., Piou, D., et al., 2007, 'Simulating the effects of a climate-change scenario on the geographical range and activity of forest-pathogenic fungi', *Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology* 29, 101-120, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07060660709507447>.

Sutherst, R.W., Maywald, G.F., Yonow, T. & Stevens, P.M., 1999. 'CLIMEX: predicting the effects of climate on plants and animals', CSIRO, Melbourne, Australia.